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**EXPERIENCES OF PARENTS IN HOME-BASED REMOTE TEACHING
USING THE MOTHER TONGUE**

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Acceptance Page

This paper prepared by **GEORGINA M. ORBETA** with the title: “**Experiences of Parents in Home-Based Remote Teaching Using the Mother Tongue**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Education, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Master of Arts in Language and Literacy Education.

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Biographical Sketch

The researcher, Georgina M. Orbeta, is from Ormoc City, Leyte. She is married and a mother of three children (soon to be four).

She is a graduate of Bachelor of Arts in Communication Arts from the University of the Philippines in the Visayas Tacloban College in 2008 and was an STFAP scholar. She finished Diploma in Teaching Secondary Education and passed the Licensure Examination for Teachers in 2016. She enrolled in the Diploma in Language and Literacy Education at the University of the Philippines Open University in 2017 and graduated in 2019. After passing the qualifying exam, she then proceeded to enroll in the Master of Arts in Language and Literacy Education. She is a recipient of the Commission on Higher Education's Scholarships for Graduate Studies.

She has been teaching Language, Communication and Literature courses at the Eastern Visayas State University-Ormoc Campus since 2012.

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*A word is dead when it is said
Some say –
I say it just begins to live That day.*
-Emily Dickinson

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Dedication

I am dedicating this thesis to my parents, Papa Ben and Mama Babie, who are no longer with me in this physical world, but their wisdom and memories still inspire me to work hard.

Next is my dear family: Robert, Sharaf, Louis, Chelsea and the soon to be born, Malaya. I have made things possible not only for myself but for us.

Lastly, I dedicate this to the young learners who need proper and quality education especially in terms of language acquisition and nurturing, and to the teachers who need to understand the importance of our mother tongues.

Abstract

The use of mother tongue (MT) as medium of instruction (MOI) and teaching it to the early grades, specifically Kindergarten to Grade 3, are one of the provisions of Mother Tongue Based-Multilingual Education as part of the provisions of the K to 12 Basic Education Program in the Philippines. Since its official implementation in school year (SY) 2012-2013, benefits and challenges have been evident in studies conducted related to its execution.

Unfortunately, the Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) greatly affected all aspects of our lives, including the education system, during the last months of SY 2019-2020. The Department of Education (DepEd) had to administer remote teaching by providing modules to learners, and had their parents teach them at home. Hence, MTB-MLE instruction continued at home. There are still limited studies and literature on how parents teach their children the MT and using it as MOI during the pandemic. This study aimed to document parents' experiences in home-based remote teaching using the mother tongue at home. The research questions are: 1) What were the parents' experiences in teaching the MT and using it as MOI during emergency remote teaching and learning setup?; 2) What strategies and techniques related to teaching the MT and using the MT as MOI did the parents use in teaching their children? and 3) What did the parents consider as benefits and challenges in teaching children the MT and using the MT MOI at home?

The study used a qualitative approach which employed a multiple case study of four parents who had children studying in Kindergarten to Grade 3 under the MTB-MLE program. Parents who represented contrasting and varied cases based on their profiles were selected. The instruments used in this study were: a survey questionnaire, interview guides and observation sheets. Data gathered were from

interviews of participants and recorded videos of their teaching sessions with their children at home. They were analyzed through inductive and thematic analysis.

The first research question on the experiences of parents in teaching the MT and using it as MOI was answered through a thematic analysis of their answers in the interviews. Five themes were generated as common experiences of the participants. These themes were: (1) difficulty and dissatisfaction in using Cebuano MT as MOI, (2) use of languages other than the Cebuano MT, (3) misconception that using Cebuano MT would be easy, (4) resourcefulness in providing Cebuano Materials, (5) use of strategies and techniques in teaching Cebuano and (6) realization that children did not know much Cebuano MT. Unique experiences were also identified for each case.

For strategies and techniques that the parents used, data from the recorded videos have shown strategies applying the following methods: Total Physical Response, Discovery Learning, Task-based Language Teaching, Content and Language Integrated Learning, Direct Method, and Audiolingual Method. Nine techniques were also used by the parents such as using the MT as MOI; using Filipino or English to explain the MT; utilizing of non-verbal techniques; using conversational; showing affection and empathy in teaching using the MT; and using appropriate physical set-up, writing tools and digital or electronic learning tools.

Benefits and challenges in teaching the MT and using it as MOI at home were found similar to the recorded advantages and disadvantages when this was implemented by teachers in the classrooms. The parents' benefits were: (1) use of the MT in teaching felt natural, (2) improvement in children's Cebuano Skills and (3) children's developed interest in the Cebuano MT. Challenges revealed were: explaining unfamiliar or difficult words, parents' prejudice against the Cebuano MT or

preference for English, absence or lack of teaching training background, and insufficient materials in Cebuano.

Keywords: Language, Mother tongue, Parents, Remote teaching

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Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Mother Tongue-based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) in the Philippines was established in 2009, and its legislation led to the adoption of the mother tongue (MT) as the medium of instruction (MOI) with 12 languages that composed the first set of official MOI (DO No. 16, s. 2012) that later became 19 in 2016 (Department of Education (DepEd), 2016). MTB-MLE in the Philippines is implemented from Kindergarten to Grade 3, and the program directs the use of the MT as the MOI in the first four years of primary education of the Learners. The program's national implementation began in school year (SY) 2012-2013 as part of the K to 12 Basic Education Program (DepEd, 2012). In 2013, Republic Act 10533, known as the Enhanced Basic Education Act, provided legal support for implementing the MTB-MLE program. It states that basic education shall be delivered in languages understood by the learners and that instructional materials and capable teachers to implement the MTB-MLE shall be made available (Official Gazette, 2013). "The program is implemented in two modes: as a learning or subject area and as medium of instruction. As MOI, the MT is used in all learning areas from Kinder to Grade 3 except in teaching Filipino and English subjects" (DepEd, 2016, Region X Press Release). Mother Tongue as a language subject focuses on the development of MT speaking, reading, and writing from Grades 1 to 3.

The program is anchored in the principle that the child can use most effectively the language he or she knows best (DO No. 74 of 2009), in other words the strongest language of the child is his or her MT (DepEd, 2013). The use of MT helps the child understand the lesson well through a familiar language, building on familiar concepts while learning both Filipino and English as second languages (Young et al., 2016). The approach can lead to developing the child to be intelligent, imaginative, and linguistically talented by acknowledging and building on the child's culture and home language and discourages exclusion and societal discrimination (Cummins, 2009 as cited in Young et al., 2016). These advantages of using the MT of the child are evident in the findings of notable empirical studies: learners learn to read more quickly when they use their first language; pupils who have learned to read and write in their first language learn to speak, read, and write in a second or third language more quickly than those who are taught in a second language; and pupils taught to read and write in their first language acquire cognitive competencies more quickly (DO No. 74 of 2009).

Using the MT is seen as the most natural and effective way of delivering knowledge and skills to children as they engage in learning processes inside and outside the school (UNESCO, 2007). Parents have an important role as partners in implementing the MTB-MLE program since they assist their children in learning the lessons outside the school. The language of the child comes from the language of his environment, and he or she learns it from his parents, who are likely to be speakers of the child's MT, and therefore, are important MT input providers to the child. The use of MT in the program encourages greater participation of parents and community members, since parents and primary caregivers have the greatest influence in the

child's language acquisitions in the beginning years (Ball, 2010). Inclusion of more local content in the curriculum is another result of using the local language in instruction, making it more relevant to the learners. Parents and community members are also encouraged to be educational resources since they can help preserve their heritage language (World Bank, 2005 as cited in UNESCO, 2007). The use and innovation of local resources in developing learning materials is highly encouraged, so that lessons and concepts are familiar to the learners, and the members of the language community themselves are the best human resources for creating materials in the MT. Involving the parents and members of the community will make instructional materials interesting and appropriate to the community's needs (Mother Tongue Based- Multilingual Education Network, 2012 as cited in Lartec, 2016). Likewise, preserving the heritage language will be attained best with the knowledge and cultural background of the elder members of society.

In 2020, MTB-MLE was already in its 8th year of implementation when, unfortunately, the infectious and fatal Novel Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) caused a pandemic that shook the global economy and affected all other aspects of people's lives. Among the many other issues that had arisen and had to be immediately addressed was that of education, how to solve the problem of school closures and the burden of education on students, parents, and teachers (Bhamani et al., 2020). Hence, due to the pandemic, the teaching-learning set-up was altered. The teachers no longer taught lessons in the traditional classroom but implemented emergency remote teaching; that is, they taught lessons using modules, and the learners were mostly assisted by their parents or guardians at home amidst the pandemic.

In the Philippines, DepEd released in May 2020 the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCS) to be used by field implementers for SY 2020-2021 to ensure

that learning standards are relevant and flexible to address the impact of COVID-19 in the basic education sector (DepEd, 2020). In addition, the Department implemented learning development modalities that can be used for each locality. The modular approach was used in educating learners. The students were provided with modules for each subject on a weekly basis in which the parents or guardians served as their tutors or teachers at home. As part of MTB-MLE implementation, the modules in kindergarten to Grade 3 used the MT as medium of instruction.

In the emergency remote teaching set-up, parents had become the teacher and facilitator of the teaching-learning process. The learners could not go to schools due to the threat of being infected by the virus. Hence, they stayed home to continue learning with their parents as the facilitator of the learning process. At home, parents became teachers, facilitators, motivators, and influencers or directors for their children in remote learning (Winingsih, 2020; Rohita and Krisnawati, 2020). However, some challenges concerning the roles of parents in this new set-up surfaced. Some parents did not have enough time to support their children in the learning process since they were busy working to earn income (Lase et al., 2021). The filial responsibilities engrained in Filipino culture required parents to prioritize the needs of the family ahead of the needs of the individual child (Blair in Bartolome et al., 2017), and some parents prioritized work for income over spending more time teaching their children.

Another study showed that parents had difficulties with balancing responsibilities, teaching and motivating learners, having access to resources, and meeting learning outcomes (Agaton & Cueto, 2021). Some parents have more than one child to assist and teach which can affect the quality and time of teaching each child. The classroom routine that learners followed before became very different.

Parents could not have the same teaching schedule that teachers implemented in the classroom since there were other things to do in the house. Before, classroom management was the responsibility of the teacher; during remote learning, the parents had to deal with managing the house so that it would be conducive for learning. A parent shared that there were too many distractions at home, from house chores to visitors, making the children unfocused (Lucenos, personal communication, March 15, 2022).

While the other issues above deserve attention, what this study considers as the more important challenges to investigate are those relating to language in the parents' remote implementation of MTB-MLE. First, most parents have no formal teaching background, or their field of expertise is different, and are not trained for this new teaching role; second, parents teaching their K-3 children usually have no knowledge and awareness about the MTB-MLE program for children to fully benefit from it.

Some might think that teaching one's own child is easy, but this task also requires some preparation to make it successful. Home teaching may have to parallel some routines and practices done in formal school, and some parents may not be aware of how to implement this. Parents are also likely to have already forgotten school lessons making it difficult to teach their children, and it is worse for parents who have not finished schooling (Joven, 2021). Also, many parents have limited awareness of program goals. Many parents are not so knowledgeable on the program policy and terminology for MTB-MLE in the Philippines (Burton, 2013). Another issue is that there are parents who speak different languages, but the instructional materials provided for the learners use a different language. There are parents who are not native speakers

of the language used in the modules, that is why some parents have difficulty comprehending the instructions in the modules and translating the language to the child's more familiar language (Dealagdon, 2021).

Furthermore, teaching requires a different, more formal register of the MT. Even teachers still need more training in delivering lessons using the MT, how much more for parents who do not have orientation on this. Parents who are not professional teachers often use casual and intimate language registers to their children, unlike teachers who use academic and formal registers to their students in the classroom setting.

Despite the challenges, some parents have become more connected to the learning journey of their children. They have become innovative and creative in assisting their children in the learning process at the comfort of their homes. Some parents have developed strategies and techniques as they adjust in the home learning set-up by designing homemade timetables so that children have a schedule to follow like a normal sleep-wake cycle and study schedule (Bhamani et al. 2020). Another strategy of parents was engaging their children to try out new things, become creative, and do more activities since they have more time for each other (Bhamani et al. 2020).

As mentioned above, among the discussed challenges faced and strategies implemented by parents, the ones that the study was concerned with were those that were related to MT use. MTB-MLE implementation should be studied especially during remote teaching that majority of the execution or teaching was conducted by the parents at home. This study fills the research gap on parents' experiences in teaching the MT subject and as MOI by documenting: the strategies and techniques they used, and the advantages and disadvantages they encountered in the teaching process.

This study investigated selected homes where the parents were facilitating the learning process using the modules for MTB-MLE and other subjects during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Moreover, it is important to document program implementation during the time of the pandemic. DepEd, teachers and parents can learn from this experience when something similar likewise forces children to study at home once again in the future. Whether there is a pandemic or not, parents are really expected to play a special role in early education, particularly in MTB-MLE implementation. Hence the data of the study are expected to be relevant even beyond emergency remote teaching and learning of the COVID pandemic.

Statement of the Problem

This study seeks to answer the following research questions:

- I. What were the parents' experiences in teaching the MT and using it as MOI during emergency remote teaching and learning set-up?
- II. What strategies and techniques related to teaching the MT and using it as MOI did the parents use in teaching their children?
- III. What did the parents consider as benefits and challenges of teaching children the MT and using it as MOI at home?

Significance of the Study

The study is important and beneficial to administrators and teachers, parents, learners, and other institutions and researchers.

Administrators and teachers

Collected data are useful to the schools since they are monitoring and evaluating their programs and the learning progress of students amidst the pandemic. This study can contribute to DepEd's goal of improving the quality and varied learning resources through the presented strategies and techniques of the parents. This also adds insights and relevant information that can give guidance for possible curriculum revision and enhancement of the MTB-MLE program. Additionally, the study helps in deepening the homeschooling program of DepEd. The Department boosted its homeschooling program in February 2022 by providing learners with their needs such as materials and favorable space for learning (Philippine News Agency, 2022). This study gains insights on practical and valuable materials for the learners that the parents and DepEd can provide. Ideas of conducive learning spaces can be sought from this study. Teachers can learn from the parents' experiences and formulate better strategies and techniques in assisting the parents in teaching their children to strengthen DepEd's support for home education.

The data gathered from this study was evaluated to document which of these experiences can be considered as best practices, and recommendations can be suggested to overcome the challenges in implementing the program. Documented strategies by the parents can be best practices and featured in teaching plans in

teaching the MT and using it as MOI at home as well as in the classroom. The teaching plans can also be useful for parents who prefer homeschooling.

The administrators of the schools can include this in their next strategic planning and as part of their agenda in meetings. Since parents are one of the major stakeholders of schools, through this study, the schools can connect more to the parents as they deal with parents' concerns. More collaboration and space for consultation can happen among teachers, parents, and the school administrators based on the recommendations of this study.

Parents

The results of the study can make the parents realize that their role in educating their children is recognized and given attention, that their opinions and experiences matter. Moreover, the identified challenges can be addressed by the school administrators. Parents have an important role in their children's continuity of learning such as in implementing MTB-MLE especially during pandemic and other emergencies when children are advised to stay home. The strategies and techniques documented in this study can be adopted by other parents.

Hence, data from the study can improve parents' critical language awareness and consciousness, especially their conception of MTB-MLE.

This study hopes to open the minds of the parents to the importance of using the MT with their children.

Learners

Learners will benefit once the recommendations of the study are addressed by the schools because teachers can use the strategies and techniques used by participant parents. It is necessary that the schools respond to the results of the study so that better strategies and techniques in teaching the learners at home or in the classroom, when face-to-face classes resume in the future, can be provided to them. The disadvantages that are connected to the challenges encountered by parents and their children, if resolved, can make the learning process better for the learners.

Other institutions and researchers

Results of this research can also be used by institutions or organizations that are concerned in advising and informing the Philippine education system on curriculum and instruction. Through the documentation of the parents' experiences, an enhancement or intervention program can be recommended for its better implementation. Results of this study add to the existing body of research that provide data that can enlighten legislation that attempts to abrogate the implementation of MTB-MLE.

In addition, qualitative studies like this, particularly in-depth, descriptive, and narrative approach on the implementation of MTB-MLE, focusing on a particular aspect that is how using the mother tongue or home language affects the learning of the children can be used at present since distance learning is being implemented due to the pandemic. It is also relevant in the future as a basis for research in developing the MTB-MLE curriculum as different learning modalities are introduced such as online learning and home-based learning. Other researchers can refer to this study and can conduct further studies related to parents' experiences in teaching the mother tongue.

Scope and Delimitations

This study focused on observing the lived experiences of five parents from Ormoc City who are teaching their Kindergarten to Grade 3 children at home using the modules provided by DepEd. Those parents taught their children at home daily or regularly, speak the same MT as their children, and have children in Kindergarten-Grade 3 in public elementary schools.

Data were gathered through interviews and ten weeks of audio and video recording sessions of home teaching. Transcribed interviews were limited to two informal, in-depth interviews per parent, and one interview per teacher to know what assistance the school and the teachers provide to the parents if there was any.

For this study, the experiences of the parents were limited to the use of MT as MOI and teaching the MT subject while teaching their children who belong to K-3 levels. These data on the parents' experiences were based on their perception during interviews and observed data from teaching sessions.

This study considered strategies to include all activities that the parents provided or engaged with their children as they taught lessons using the MT at home. The techniques included the materials and tools used by the parents in doing the activities as they taught their children in MT MOI and as guided by the modular approach of DepEd. Also, the benefits and challenges that were documented were limited to the teaching experiences of the parents as they taught their children using MT at home. What were advantageous were those that made the teaching and learning process easy and successful for both the parents and learners. On the other hand, those referred to as disadvantageous were those that made the teaching and

learning process difficult and unsuccessful for the parents in teaching their children using MT at home.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This chapter describes the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) implementation in the Philippines before and how the situation in teaching and learning using the MT changed during the pandemic. The role of parents is very important during remote teaching since they have become the teachers and implementers of the program. It also discusses parents' experiences, challenges, strategies, and techniques they used in teaching the MT and using it as MOI during emergency remote teaching and learning set-up. There is also a discussion on Vygotsky's theory of social constructivism, home learning environment and parental involvement that highlights the importance of parents' role in educating their children.

Mother tongue based-multilingual education implementation in the Philippines

Multilingual Education (MLE) is the use of two or more languages for literacy and instruction which was based on the principle of starting where the learners are, and from what they already know (Nolasco, 2016). The MTB-MLE program was firmly established in the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 (RA 10533) as part of the K to 12 program (Monje et al., 2019).

Teaching children using the MT in early childhood and primary education has been encouraged by UNESCO since 1953 (UNESCO, 1953 as cited by Ball, 2010). Mother-tongue based schooling is important in achieving educational quality (Benson,

2005). Using the MT in the early years in the acquisition and development of literacy skills, with the students' being able to understand and participate in class discussions, is one common element in bilingual models and practices (Benson, 2004). Bilingual schooling has brought benefits in terms of teaching practices which have been published in academic journals (see reviews in Baker 2001; Cummins 2000; CAL 2001 as cited in Benson, 2004).

The Philippines, being a multilingual country with around 185 languages spoken, found the necessity to adopt the program which has been supported by research to benefit learners. The history of successfully coming up with the MTB-MLE program in the country can be traced from the Bilingual Education Policy in 1974 to the formally launched Multilingual Education Policy. This development in the language education policy in the Philippines, which is indicated in Department of Education (DepEd) Order No. 74 series of 2009, is the Institutionalization of MTB-MLE (Walter and Dekker, 2011). With this, the country had taken its steps in having MT instruction as a way to elevate the quality of education (UNESCO 2003). Regional Directors and Superintendents were instructed to assist in the promotion and encouragement of the local community to support the MLE (DepEd Order (DO) 74 series of (s.) 2009). DO 74 s. 2009 enclosed the fundamental requirements for a strong MTB-MLE.

The MTB-MLE program's goal is to develop learners' MT vocabulary. The goals of students are to use the MT to achieve quality education, to become confident in the use of MT in the classroom; to learn to read and write in their MT, to begin learning the official school language then read and write it, and to learn the other languages necessary in the curriculum (Malone, 2018). A major principle of the program is the "development of literacy and numeracy skills and learning of concepts

initially in the MT from the first grade until third grade and later transfer to second language (Filipino and English)” (DO 31 s. 2012, Enclosure No. 1, p. 1).

In school year (SY) 2012-2013, the MTB-MLE program was officially implemented throughout the country with 12 new mother tongues (Tagalog, Kapampangan, Pangasinense, Iloko, Bikol, Cebuano, Hiligaynon, Waray, Tausug, Maguindanaoan, Meranao, and Chabacano) (D.O. 16 s. 2012). In July 2013, seven languages: Ybanag, Ivatan, Sambal, Aklanon, Kinaray-a, Yakan, and Surigaonon were added, making the total number of mother tongues to 19 (8 Lingua Francas and 11 Local Languages) (DO No. 28 s. 2013).

“The MTB-MLE program is implemented in two modes: as a learning or subject area and as medium of instruction; as MOI, the MT is used in all learning areas from Kinder to Grade 3 except in teaching Filipino and English subjects” (DepEd, 2016, p. 1). Additionally, the program has the aim to improve the learner’s language and cognitive development and at the same time his or her socio-cultural awareness (DO No. 28, s. 2013, p. 1).

For the program to be successfully implemented, the parents and primary caregivers need to do their part in helping the child acquire his first language in the beginning years (Ball, 2010). The immediate environment of the child has a strong influence on his language acquisition and literacy. Hence, part of the requirements for a strong MTB-MLE program is to make sure that the local government unit, parents, and the community participate and give their support for the implementation of the language and literacy program strategy (DO No. 74, s. 2009). The first teachers of the children are their family members who have an important role in their education. It is important to research on the roles of informal and non-formal education and how

families interact with each other to promote literacy, numeracy, and higher order cognitive skills using the MT (Ball, 2010). It is through language that these members of society communicate to children, and these children develop their knowledge through the use of language (Morin, 2012).

Considering the factors that affect the success of MTB-MLE program implementation, it can be expected that challenges can be encountered if they are not fulfilled. It is important to discuss the challenges and how they were overcome before and during remote teaching and learning.

Challenges and strategies in the implementation of mother tongue-based multilingual education before the pandemic

The literature yields four classifications of challenges in the implementation of the MTB-MLE program categorized as 1) limited or no background knowledge and misconception of the program and educational system's execution of the policy, 2) teacher training and instruction, 3) language bias, and 4) teaching and learning materials (Burton, 2013; Ball, 2010 as cited in Espada and Vivero, 2017; Monje et al., 2019). These challenges complement and are related to the four dimensions of challenges namely language, instruction, materials, and program cited in a previous study (Williams et al., 2014).

For the first challenge on limited or no background knowledge of the program, advocates, or proponents of the MTB-MLE in different parts of the world encountered people who thought that the program was not necessary, and it was impossible to implement. There was also a challenge in the educational system's execution of policy such that teachers found it difficult to follow the policy of using only the MT in lessons

for Grade 1 (Burton, 2013). There was no proper transfer of the philosophy behind the program and the way it should be taught to the teachers and parents, resulting them to depend much on translation to convey meaning even though according to 2009 DepEd order, MTB-MLE's essence is not on being able to translate words (Burton, 2013). In addition, the educational system's execution of policy language priorities in school and at home were incompatible because parents let their children speak English at home instead of the MT which was given importance at school in the early years (Espada et al., 2017). The two stakeholder groups of particular interest in the implementation of the program are the teachers and the parents because they are the closest people who the child interacts with often (Burton, 2013). Therefore, it is important that the teachers and parents have sufficient knowledge of the program. However, most parents lacked enough knowledge about language in education policy (Ansre and Klu, 2017) and they expressed more limited awareness of MTB-MLE (Burton, 2013).

A strategy to make the parents become aware of the program was by inviting them to attend meetings that helped them learn about the advantages of using the MT as MOI, and made them trust the program (Metila et al., 2016). Additionally, developing collaboration among the offices in the region and division level, and letting parents and members of the community convene regularly so that they can participate in the plans of the school were very helpful (Williams et al., 2014). In Bangladesh, non-governmental organizations with the help of UNESCO, arranged a workshop at the regional level to make the different members of the community, including people from tribes and workers in the education sector, become aware about MLE (UNESCO, 2007).

Adding to the challenges at the ground level was the training of teachers who were teaching the learners. Teacher training is one of the factors that affect the success of mother tongue-based bi/multilingual education policies (Ball, 2011). Training of many teachers on MTB-MLE had been done a month only before it was implemented in the Philippines in 2012; and that instruction on the teaching in the MT was insufficient in the first few years of implementation (Monje et al., 2019). In addition, there was limited use of the MT for academic purposes, teachers had low proficiency in the MT and had difficulty distinguishing learning competencies (Williams et al., 2014). Parents also claimed that there was a widening gap in the scaffolding process because some words in the materials provided by DepEd were not being used at home during family conversations (Espada, et al., 2017). The teachers were not prepared to deal with the difficulty they encountered in teaching the MT. The students found it hard to learn the MT when they were exposed to not the same languages in their school and at home (Espada, et al., 2017).

A strategy that helped teachers with low competence in using the MT included the use of informal activities depending on teacher resourcefulness and initiative. For instance, some strategies of teachers were taking time to read materials in the MT, listening to local radio programs that used the MT, and learning the MT through formal instruction. (Metila et al., 2016). To overcome the language-related challenges in MTB-MLE implementation, teachers used strategies such as the translation of the target language to the more familiar language and the use of multilingual teaching and lingua franca (Lartec et al., 2014). Teachers also had consultation time with students and let students speak their mother tongue, or Filipino (Baring, personal communication, March 22, 2022). One strategy that can teach and enhance the use

of MT was to let the parents use it often at home (Metila et al., 2016). Parents should read MT texts to their children. Children who had greater relative exposure to their MT at home (compared to a second language) experienced more growth in the former's vocabulary (Goodrich et al., 2021). The books that children preferred to read were those that were interesting, and related to their life and their local community, not just any storybook (Ofosu-Dankyi, 2017). In Cambodia, part of their strategies in teaching the MT was utilizing Whole Language activities by using Big Books, storytelling about language experience, listening to stories and doing creative writing sessions (UNESCO, 2007).

Aside from the fact that the teachers had difficulty using the MT, there was also the challenge of language bias, not only of the teachers but also of the parents. The main cause for the MTB-MLE policy to lose its effectiveness was the great desire of parents to learn foreign languages to have greater income in the future (Ball, 2010 as cited in Espada et al., 2017). Although some parents understood the benefits of using the MT in the early years of education to acquire a second language, they were still concerned about the opportunities of their children if they learn English better (Burton, 2013). In areas where local minor languages were spoken, parents had stated clearly that they preferred usage of English in Math subjects (Williams et al., 2014). Some parents did not use the MT and did not show support in the chosen medium of instruction (MOI) which is the MT (Monje et al., 2019). Based on misconceptions about the learning of language, parents feared that their children may not be able to use English or Filipino since they were learning more about the MT (Metila et al., 2016). Many parents and teachers had language bias, in that they thought being good in using English means having more privileges and opportunities (Burton, 2013).

For this language misconception, the same strategy for the first challenge was applicable which was conducting information dissemination activities about the program and creating ways to clarify the essential principles and research support for MTB-MLE (Metila et al., 2016). Other strategies included information campaigns using streamers, consultations with the parents through the General Parents Teachers Association assembly, Home Room Parents Teachers Association meeting, Parents and Teachers Conference and Orientation, and orientation seminars to the parents of Grade 1 pupils during the pilot implementation of MTB-MLE in 2011 (Metila et al., 2016).

Lastly, there were limited teaching materials necessary to implement the program. The top reasons of the schools which responded to a survey conducted by Philippine Institute for Development Studies and were not implementing the program, were related to resources such as insufficient supply of needed teaching materials, unavailability of dictionaries of the MT, and lacking textbooks for students (Monje et al., 2019). While for those who had implemented the program, they lacked materials in the MT that had appropriate context which resulted in using questionable strategies and techniques (Espada and Vivero, 2017), and insufficient mother tongue instructional materials (IMs) (Dio and Jamora, 2014). Therefore, with insufficient materials, children's development of reading skills was sacrificed; for example, in Ghana, teachers had difficulty teaching the MT since they did not have enough MT books in their schools (Ofosu-Dankyi, 2017). This was also true for Chinese nationalities wherein the lack of printed literature and instructional materials in minority languages had become an obstacle to bilingual education (UNESCO, 2007). Furthermore, challenges regarding materials were: 1) lacking and delayed delivery of instructional materials (IMs) in MT, 2) limited use of technology, 3) time and expenses

demanding by materials production (wherein parents had to contribute for materials expenses), 4) teacher's guides (TGs) were in English, and 5) learning materials (LMs) did not match the MT of the pupils (Williams et al., 2014). One of the challenges regarding materials was that the words used in the materials were not familiar to the students and parents (Metila et al., 2016). Also, the publishers did not have the capacity to supply reading materials in the MTs (Arzadon et al., 2020) which became the reason for having limited printed materials in the MT.

The answer to the problem of what kinds of materials and content in the materials to include will be solved by the community themselves like in a minority community in China. Leaders and teachers of the Kam community shared knowledge of their language and culture which helped develop a wide range of curriculum and instructional materials (UNESCO, 2007). In the Philippines, one strategy for the challenge of materials was the initiative of parents to buy an MT dictionary so that learners can refer to it when they encountered difficult MT words, and some parents bought MT reading materials that the teachers can reproduce (Metila et al., 2016). In addition, the teachers improvised instructional materials written in the MT, and used literary pieces written in the MT to motivate learners (Lartec et al., 2014). Other strategies were utilizing funds of the school (e.g., MOOE) for producing materials, using magazines of the local community to supplement MT resource materials, inviting parents to contribute for materials production and to donate MT books (Williams et al., 2014). Nevertheless, DepEd ensured that appropriate and contextualized materials were available at the school level (D.O. 21, series of 2019). To solve the delay in materials production, some regions had decided to draft their own quality assurance guidelines so that materials were localized, and materials validation was done within the region (Metila et al., 2016).

MTB-MLE implementation in the Philippines during the pandemic

The Corona virus which began spreading in December 2019 had disrupted the education system globally and had greatly affected more than 1.5 billion students (UNESCO, 2020). Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the system of educating children has changed. The closure of educational institutions had greatly affected more than 94% of the world's student population (Pokhrel and Chhetri, 2021). Since lockdowns had to be implemented, parents started to work from home and spent more time with their children making the communication between parents and children more important and critical (Aykanat and Omeruglo, 2021).

As part of the adjustments during emergency remote teaching and learning, the Philippines had adopted distance learning, emergency remote teaching and education using the modular approach. Since the school year 2020-2021, DepEd has provided Self-Learning Modules that the students can use to continue delivering lessons to learners.

On May 5, 2020, the Learning Continuity Plan was introduced by DepEd to manage the new normal set-up of continuing basic education through the Learning Continuity Plan (LCP) when School Year 2020-2021 opened on August 24, 2020 (DepEd, 2020).

The set-up of teaching and learning delivery had been greatly affected due to the pandemic. Distance learning had affected both parents and their children (Campbell, 2020; Chung et al., 2020 as cited in Schmidt et al., 2021). Hence, the implementation of MTB-MLE in the Philippines had also been challenged since parents became the major people implementing the program at home.

The school opening in August 2020 was not like the traditional face-to-face classes but was dependent on the risk severity grading or classification of a locality,

in accordance with the Department of Health (DOH), the Inter-Agency Task Force for the Management of Infectious Diseases (IATF), and the Office of the President (OP) guidelines (D.O. No. 07 s. 2020). The learning delivery modalities used by the schools depended on the COVID-19 health protocols of a specific place and learners' condition (D.O. 12 s. 2020).

In addition, division offices, schools, collaborators in the community, students and their parents were guided by the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) of DepEd to become more equipped to face the challenges caused by COVID-19 (D.O. No. 12 series of 2020). Part of this Continuity Plan was the adoption of the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCS), an emergency measure to allow instruction during challenging situations like the pandemic (DepEd, 2020). Also, at the regional level, a memo was issued inviting parents and teachers to learn more about how they can do their duties in the distance learning delivery modalities through a virtual orientation for the Visayas cluster (DepEd Region 8, 2020). This online orientation aimed to deepen the discussion on parents and learning facilitators in different learning delivery modalities and understand better the key concepts and challenges in delivering these modalities in the new normal set-up as well as the ways to overcome these challenges (DepEd, 2020).

DepEd made sure that materials were available online and offline for the new normal. For the whole Philippines, "DepEd has story books through storybook competition writing, Kindergarten Activity Sheets, ADM K Learning Kit and Primer Lessons for Grade 1, Grade 1 English - Activity Sheets, Learning Materials (LMs) and Teacher's Guides (TGs) for kindergarten to Grade 3 learners" (DepEd, 2020, p. 33). For K-3 materials, Alternative Delivery Mode (ADM) learning modules for K (Kindergarten Learning Experiences-KCEP Module) to Grade 3 and Primer in 19

languages were provided (DepEd, 2020, p. 33). However, according to some teachers in Ormoc City they were not able to participate in the storybook writing competition during the pandemic. For Region VIII, they received these ADM modules and activity sheets for Kindergarten to Grade 3. Some of the teachers were asked to participate in content creation for the materials to be distributed during the pandemic (Baring, personal communication, March 16, 2022).

In August 2020, an online writeshop was conducted on the finalization of DepEd Developed Learning Materials (DLLMs) Bridging Primer for Grade II to make sure that quality basic education was continued despite the pandemic (DepEd, 2020). Moreover, DepEd launched in February 2021 a free online tutorial platform called the ETUlay for learners and parents; and one of its goals was to empower and make the parents confident in assisting their children during the pandemic (DepEd, 2021). Some teachers were informed about the ETUlay program, but they did not take advantage of its benefits.

In addition to developing materials for instruction in the new normal, the Department also came up with the idea of hiring support teachers for the primary grades. Kindergarten to Grade 3 learners depend heavily on adults as the ones who take care of them and facilitate their early education. Part of the written strategies for K-3 on the Department's plan was the option of having para-teachers for modular learning at home who should undergo training to be ready in the teaching task (DepEd, 2020). A Facilitator's guide was provided to the para-teachers. In Ormoc City, there were teacher aides or teaching support staff to help the teachers in their teaching work. These aides were those who applied for a teaching position at DepEd and were still waiting to be hired. They received an allowance from the local government. Some of them were assigned to visit the homes of the children to help the parents in the

teaching process. Most of the time, the parents were still the ones who provided learning activities and taught the lessons to their children using the modules.

To better implement the learning delivery modalities, DepEd conducted regular Parent-Teacher Conferences so that there will be collaboration among the members of the community and to make sure that parents support school in plans (DepEd, 2020). In February 2021, DepEd called for the creation of the MTB-MLE support for the development of storybooks in the local languages which improves the capacity of schools and communities (DepEd Region 8, 2021). The Summer Institute of Linguistic-Language Education and Development (SIL-LEAD) committed to help in building the capacity of 90 recipient schools and communities in developing storybooks in the local languages (DepEd, 2021). In the same month, the Department issued a memorandum on the inventory of MTB-MLE learning resources since the regional offices and the local community were greatly involved in developing these relevant resources (DepEd, 2021).

Language teaching approaches and methods

The literature provides several language teaching approaches and methods on which language teaching strategies may be based. Among these are: Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), Discovery Learning, Experiential Learning, Content and Language Integrated Language Learning (CLIL), Direct Method, Audiolingual Method (ALM), Total Physical Response (TPR). In addition, there are reading comprehension strategies such as the gradual release model and use of narrative and informational texts that are helpful in implementing MTBMLE. The following discussions define each method, give examples of activities applying the method, explain how it is related to MTB-MLE program implementation, and provide studies that support its effectiveness

in relation to language learning. The first methods use real-life contexts such as CLT, Discovery Learning, Experiential Learning, and CLIL. These are followed by more traditional methods such as Direct Method and ALM, and finally a humanistic method like the TPR.

CLT is based on the theory that communication is the main purpose of language (“Principles of Communicative Language Teaching,” 2007) and developing communicative competence is its central concept (Hymes, 1971 as cited in Savignon, 2015). Communicative competence refers to having the social skills to interact with others, considering other social factors as place, purpose, occasion, and people involved (Rambe, 2017 & Savignon, 2015). Communicative language learning strategies include well-selected and sensitive performance tasks involving real situations that help achieve goals (Sukyng, 2021). Task-based approach (TBA) applies the principles of CLT by giving tasks which are related to a child’s reality or experiences which involve problem solving and personal sharing while learning a language (Mao, 2012). TBA works by having students perform tasks within their realities using the target language to be learned (Sanchez, 2004) which according to Skelii (2001) “has a real-world relationship.” Using real examples to meet the goal of learning a language is very applicable for using and learning the MT. In the MTB-MLE program, it is good to use local contexts that are close to the reality of the learner. A study revealed results that using communicative interactive tasks have developed students’ speaking by developing their motivation and confidence to speak (Torky, 2006). Another study that tested the use of a task-based approach on students learning English as a second language has shown great improvements in their test scores (Kartini et al., 2020). Aside from this approach that uses real-world

experiences, there is another method that encourages students to use available materials around them through discovery.

Discovery learning is an educational method that gives instruction based on inquiry using a constructivist approach (Singaravelu, 2012). It encourages student participation in deciding what, how, and when things are to be learned which is proven to have a positive effect on students' listening skills (Hanafi, 2016). This is principle number 4 of DepEd's guiding principles in teaching and learning MTB-MLE which is about having knowledge and applying that to learn a new concept or idea (DepEd, 2016). For example, students are given an activity that lets them use available materials in their surroundings to create a kind of artwork. They need to be attentive to the instruction of the teacher to come up with the needed output. The use of discovery learning has proven to improve students' listening and affective scores (Hanafi, 2016). The next approach is related to giving students opportunities to discover the realities of the world.

Experiential Learning is an approach that is student-centered, requiring students' cooperation by learning from each other by means of direct experiences in connection to problems in the real world (Kolb & Kolb, 2009 as cited in Wright, 2015). This encourages active involvement of learners as they engage in authentic experiences and make evaluations of their performance. During the pandemic, when parents were the ones facilitating the learning activities of their children, this method was suggested to be used ("5 ways to do experiential," 2021). At home, parents with young learners can read books available at home, grow plants together, learn simple biology concepts, cook together, and identify names of ingredients, and take a walk outside and have art activities ("5 ways to do experiential," 2021). MTB-MLE's fifth principle is Active Learning that encourages students to learn and work with peers and

engages them in meaningful talk (DepEd, 2016). In a study conducted with Grade 6 pupils who participated in experiential learning activities, it was found that involvement in the said activities have positive effects to their attitudes towards math learning and had good effects to their academic progress (Uyen et al., 2022). While experiential learning engages students in many activities that they can easily relate to, CLIL is another approach that engages them in more meaningful learning using contexts based on reality.

The Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) is an approach that uses more than one language for teaching and learning which applies Halliday's three main interdependent processes: learning language, learning through language, and learning about language (Halliday, 1993 as cited in Urmeneta, 2019). It is a method that teaches content or subject areas and at the same time lets learners learn a language which effectively teaches two subjects to the learner ("10 best language teaching strategies," n.d.). An example is teaching students science using the English language. The students learn English grammar, spelling, and vocabulary while learning about science lessons. This is done in MTB-MLE wherein students learn how to use their mother tongue while learning other subject areas such as mathematics and science. At a primary school in Sweden where CLIL was used in a study, it was proven to be an effective method in improving oral communication skills, understanding lessons, and increasing awareness of one's own culture, heightened skills in oral communication and cognition, increased intercultural awareness, and language development (Porc, 2020). Aside from the methods that use real-life contexts, there are traditional methods for language learning.

The Direct Method lets students use the target language and requires them to speak and think in that language ("Language teaching strategies, n.d.). Among the

strategies involved in using this method are having questions and answers and reading aloud sessions with correction of pronunciation and grammar. Just like the task-based approach, this method encourages the use of real-life contexts so that students are encouraged to speak and think in the target language (Mart, 2013). Teachers have a great role in the implementation of the direct method, such as having students achieve oral mastery before introducing spelling or written texts (Richardson, 1983). The success of this method depends on the language proficiency of the teacher, being able to speak the target language well and applying some verbal and non-verbal techniques in teaching (Mart, 2013). For the success of implementation of MTB-MLE, teachers should be equipped with skills on how to execute the method well with proficiency in the MT. A study revealed that the Direct Method has a positive effect on students' speaking skills, improving their pronunciation, vocabulary, and grammar (Andriyani, 2015). The next traditional method is the audiolingual method.

The Audiolingual Method (ALM) which can be traced back to BF Skinner's Theory of Behaviorism, talks about training human beings through a system of reinforcement, wherein positive feedback is received for correct behavior and negative feedback is provided for incorrect behavior (Alemi, 2016). ALM involves an oral approach in teaching a language by repeatedly letting the learner pronounce words for familiarization of sound and patterns (Bateman and Lago, 2012). Examples of activities for ALM are letting students recite poems, making them read a short story aloud, and instructing them to count numbers orally. The teacher lets them stop if they mispronounce words, correct the mistake, and give them a low score; but if they do well, they get a high score. This is connected to the principle of MTB-MLE on language and academic development which has a goal of developing children's skills in the first language to help them achieve better academically. Being able to speak using proper

pronunciation is part of the academic achievement of students in their first language. Through ALM, they can learn to speak and be confident to use their first language with accurate pronunciation and intonation. In addition, the program encourages the use of hearing, speaking, reading, and writing in activities that focus on meaning and accuracy, in which ALM can be used (DepEd, 2016). ALM has been found effective for Grade 8 students who learned English using this method; their score in speaking improved, and their pronunciation and grammar were also developed (Rahmah, 2016). The next is a humanistic method for language learning.

The Total Physical Response method (TPR) uses speaking and physical activities to teach language since it can be acquired by using activities involving movements (Richards & Rodgers, 2001). To teach language or vocabulary, TPR lets the learner use his or her body parts to react to what the teacher says ("Total Physical Response," n.d.). Examples for TPR activities include games that let young learners use their body, use their memory and at the same time enjoy themselves while learning (Er, 2012). One of the principles of MTB-MLE is cognitive development which can be achieved by using higher order thinking skills (HOTS) in the classroom activities. TPR can be used to apply HOTS depending on students' age and capacity. According to a study, this method was helpful for students in achieving learning outcomes at school (Celik et al., 2021).

Aside from the mentioned language methods and strategies, there are suggested reading comprehension strategies for mother tongue education such as the gradual release model and use of different types of texts for reading comprehension (The Reading Comprehension Interest Group, 2021). The gradual release model is based on scaffolding instruction wherein the teacher gives

instructions, models how these are done, then lets the students do the task on their own until they can do it. The texts used for developing students' reading comprehension are informational and narrative texts which teach learners to identify cause and effect, make predictions, and sequence events (The Reading Comprehension Interest Group, 2021). These strategies can be used by parents as they facilitate learning at home for their children's reading comprehension for the MT. After presenting the methods applied in language teaching strategies, the next section presents strategies that parents used during remote teaching.

Parents' teaching experiences using the mother tongue during remote teaching

There are still limited published literature or articles about parents' teaching experiences during the pandemic. Most of the literature talk about parents' general experience during the pandemic such as undergoing different kinds of stress and challenges related to managing time at home as they teach children; not much literature has been published about the strategies and techniques in teaching using the MT MOI. There were practical experiences of Filipino parents during remote teaching documented in recent studies. Some parents had to take their personal approach on how to teach their children (Cahapay, 2021). That is, they tried to teach their children using the manner of teaching that they had been taught. They only had limited ideas on the methods of teaching. In addition, parents claimed having trouble motivating and disciplining their children at home (Misirli and Ergulec, 2021). Since their children felt at ease and relaxed in doing the schoolwork at home, they did not study at home seriously, making them hard to discipline. In a study of lived experiences of parents in the implementation of modular distance learning, parents shared about experiences in getting important information about school activities using

Facebook as their means of being connected with the teachers and parents to cope with their struggles in distance learning (Paco et al., 2021). Also, parents had developed time management skills during the pandemic by doing responsibilities at home while teaching their children how to answer module tasks. Planning and dividing their time in the responsibilities at home were their way to overcome the struggles (Paco et al., 2021).

There is a need to investigate MTB-MLE implementation at the time that most of the execution of teaching is done by the parents at home. The previous section discussed that implementation of the program already had many challenges even before the pandemic, more so in the remote teaching set-up with parents facing varied challenges. This study fills this research gap or the underexplored area on the experiences of Filipino parents who taught their children the MT and used the MT as MOI.

Some strategies that were helpful to parents in teaching using the MT MOI at home during the pandemic were: 1) consulting with the school and teachers on MT MOI, 2) providing fun activities and routines for the children using MT, 3) using own experiences and culture in teaching the MT, 4) improving communication with children, and 5) taking advantage of online resources to better teach the MT (Kolac et al., 2021; Bhamani et al., 2020; Orgiles et al., 2020 as cited in Aykanat and Omeroglu, 2021). The following sections discuss the strategies that parents used in teaching children the MT during the pandemic:

The first strategy, consulting with the school and teachers on MT MOI which was distinguished as one of the most important aspects of distance learning (Kolac et al., 2021). Parents shared the importance of support networks as part of the homeschool experience (Johnson, 2021). In a case study of parents' digital spaces, it

was revealed that having good virtual networks was advantageous to the welfare of people especially in difficult contexts like during the pandemic (Hila and Baldich, 2021). Fortunately, there were various efforts to support parents as they teach their children at home such as conducting regular meetings with parents virtually through webinars. DepEd, through the External Partnerships Service (EPS), made sure that strategies and techniques were provided to parents to enhance their teaching experiences at home through a PTA webinar titled “Parents’ Role for a Better Learning at Home” and establishment of home learning spaces for SY 2021-2022 (DepEd, 2021). During Parents and Teachers meeting before the start of School Year 2020-2021, topics such as teaching children how to read using the MT as MOI were included to give parents an idea of the teaching process (Omega, personal communication, March 18, 2022).

Providing fun activities and routines for the children is another strategy of parents. The somehow limitless time that the pandemic has brought has become a unique opportunity for parents and their children to try out new things and ideas (Bhamani et al., 2020). The pandemic made schooling activities challenging to carry out, yet parents continued to provide learning activities for their children, which was done more by the mothers (Rohita and Kriswanati, 2020). Mothers were more involved in teaching their children and they felt more capable than fathers at managing school-related tasks (Kolac et al., 2021). Both parents should be creative in coming up with a system in the family’s daily schedule when it comes to educating children during the pandemic so that children will not be bored and family life is considered (Schmidt et al., 2021). Some parents found it necessary that their children sleep and wake up at the same time by following a regular schedule (Bhamani et al., 2020).

Another approach was using own experiences and culture in teaching by sharing parents' unique experiences to their children in the teaching sessions such as using examples that were related to the family's culture. Utilizing the MT develops the child's connection with family, society, culture, and identity by being able to accept oneself through an understanding of social origin and character using the home language (Nishanthi, 2020). Parents consulted neighbors and relatives to help children learn about their mother tongue (Dealagdon, 2021). Some bilingual families used school books to teach their MT to their children and explained regional idiomatic expressions that the children heard and did not understand (Da Silva, 2014). They also exposed their children to their home language by using materials that are found at home such as books, magazines, and digital materials (Da Silva, 2014). During the pandemic, efforts were also made by Indigenous People's Education Office (IPsEO) and IP Education Focal Persons of the Philippines to help indigenous people access learning materials, and one good resource for content was the immediate family (Ingle, 2020). Moreover, there were many foundations and non-profit organizations that offered assistance to parents in teaching their children using the MT. HundrED, a non-profit organization, worked closely with parents in the community of Uganda and Kenya to help them understand that local language literacy will better prepare their children for the future (HundrED, 2021). Lastly, there are also activities that can let the children learn to appreciate their own culture by singing songs in the MT and playing traditional games that use words in the MT. Some children love it when their parents are their teachers and become inspired to learn more (Tan, 2020).

Improving communication and ways of dealing with children is also beneficial when teaching children at home. During the quarantine, calmness of family members and parents in speaking and communicating made it easier for children to deal with

the pandemic (Orgiles et al., 2020 as cited in Aykanat and Omeroglu, 2021). Parents used different techniques to make learning fun and more understandable for their children. Children have to be excited about reading and learning and the way for this to happen is through activities which are understandable and enjoyable for them (Nishanthi, 2020). Reading stories on the internet, playing games that involve the use of the MT and calling relatives who speak the MT were some of the things that parents did (Bhamani et al., 2020). At home, there are also strategies that parents can do to motivate their bilingual children to use their mother tongue. Among them are talking to one another in the MT and using it to show that one practices the language as well, doing storytelling using family photos and talking about the things in the photo, calling their grandparents or relatives, and speaking only in the MT through video calls (Tan, 2020). One way that parents can teach the MT to their children was by letting them hear the language more such that parents regularly talked to them in the MT (Cross 2009 as cited in Crew, 2020).

Lastly, taking advantage of technology to help them in their concerns about how to teach the MT to their children. There are many videos on the Internet, particularly on YouTube that orient parents on how to teach their children at home. For example, there is a video on “How to Teach Beginner Readers in Filipino Mother Tongue-Based Instructions” (Teacher Jen, 2021). There are also Facebook groups and pages that can be sources of materials in teaching children at home such as the MTB-MLE Advocates and the MTB-MLE Sinugbuanong Binisaya. Other parents still taught their MT to their children although their family was residing in a Filipino-speaking place (Arzadon, 2020). This was shown in a video uploaded via Facebook about a child reading a Cebuano text although their family was already residing in Laguna.

After presenting the situation of MTB-MLE implementation before the pandemic and looking into the parents' experiences using the mother tongue to teach their children during remote teaching, we can see that the challenges involved in both periods involve the same elements. The elements such as program, language and materials discussed very similar concerns except for instruction which required different settings and persons who deliver the lessons. Before the pandemic, the main facilitators of learning were the teachers, and the setting was in the classroom or school; while during remote teaching, the parents were the teachers, and the setting was in their homes. These details on the challenges and strategies that teachers and parents experienced informed the study of what areas or elements need to be explored.

Benefits and challenges of teaching in the MT at home during the pandemic

The remote teaching and learning set-up and with parents as main implementers of MTB-MLE have benefits to parents such as: 1) becoming more involved in the education of their children, 2) having more emotional bond with their children (Cahapay, 2021), and 3) having more time to practice using the MT (Dillon, 2021). The challenges were: 1) the multiple roles of parents at home that sacrifice the quality of teaching they provide to their children (Winingsih, 2020; Rohita and Krisnawati, 2020), 2) parents' low proficiency in the academic register of the MT for teaching (Luceños, personal communication, March 22, 2022), and 3) parents' lack of training in teaching the MT to their children (Abuhammad, 2020).

The following paragraphs discuss the benefits that parents experienced in teaching their children during the COVID-19 pandemic:

The first benefit was parents had become more involved in educating their children, the parent and the child were more connected in the learning process (Cahapay, 2021). Some parents enjoyed working with their children and found it rewarding when their children thrived (Johnson, 2021). Some parents thought that learning from home was advantageous in terms of being able to talk and listen to their children, having the opportunity to do new activities, learning together, and witnessing how their child adapted to new situations (Nayir and Sari, 2020).

Second, parents had more emotional bonds with their children. The learning process happening at home did not only result in physical attachment but also emotional bond between the parent and the child (Cahapay, 2021). When the parents and their children have more natural and meaningful conversations using the MT, they become closer with their children. Parents can also read texts in the MT to their children. According to research, reduced dropout rates can be achieved by means of teaching the child to read in the MT early, and learning can be more interesting for children when the MT is used (*Ofosu-Dankyi, 2017*).

Third, parents had more time to practice using the MT. The greater time spent for home learning gives an opportunity to develop new practices that sustain community culture and language of the home (Dillon, 2021). Another advantage of having children stay at home is that they can pick up and use the MT of the family. Children, being always at home, had more chances of hearing their parents' MT; and they were using the languages of their parents more because of the pandemic, particularly those younger children (Hardach, 2020). Parents at home who spoke their heritage language can be heard more often by their children during the lockdown (Afreem and Norton, 2021). In fact, for immigrant parents to transmit and maintain their heritage language, looking at their mother language positively was a great factor (Da

Silva, 2014). It is really at home where the children spend more time during the pandemic, where the children develop and sustain their language.

On the other hand, a challenge of remote teaching and learning set-up in teaching the MT was parents' having multiple roles at home. Parents around the world had experienced various kinds of adjustments and challenges as they took the roles of teachers at home. Parents played multiple roles such as, facilitator, motivator, and influencer or director by guiding their children in remote learning (Winingsih, 2020; Rohita and Krisnawati, 2020). Parents reported taking on new roles with unique challenges in teaching (Weaver and Swank, 2021). Parents had never yet been obliged to take on such a role in education, whereas now they need to constantly communicate to the school, particularly to the teachers, to assist them in teaching their children (Kolac et al., 2021). Parents had become more burdened economically, psychologically, and socially because of distance learning (Lase et al., 2020). In a study published in 2021, 32% of the 10, 545 parents of the Republic of Croatia were unable to look after lessons and tasks that teachers provide, and 35% were exhausted and stressed (Kolac et al., 2021). It can even be more difficult for parents with children at various learning stages to monitor their children and attend to their needs at home compared to parents with an only child (Aykanat and Omeroglu, 2021).

The second challenge was parents' low proficiency in the academic register of the MT for teaching. Parents found it difficult to explain the lessons in the module since the terms used were not familiar to them (Luceños, personal communication, March 22, 2022). This is related to the problem of material development of the MT even before the pandemic. Not all the variants of a language were used in the materials development; for instance, Cebuano has many variants like

Sinugbuanong Bisaya, Boholano, Southern Leyte and Cagayan de Oro Binisaya. DepEd has produced materials for the 19 major languages only which includes the Sinugbuanong Binisaya (DepEd, 2016). However, the modules distributed in Ormoc included Binisaya of the Cagayan people or of other variants of Cebuano which may not be familiar to Ormocanons.

Lastly, there was a challenge in the parents' way of handling distance learning techniques especially in using the MT materials, and there was no trained person to help them (Abuhammad, 2020). Many low-income parents during the pandemic at Springboard Collaborative, a nonprofit based in Philadelphia which has helped close the literacy gap by bridging the gap between home and school, were unable to read books to their children due to literacy and language problems (Seale, 2020). Also, Chinese parents complained about not being trained or not being ready to adopt online learning, hence they viewed distance and online learning as challenging (Dong et al., 2020 as cited in Cahapay 2021). In the Philippines, there was a school shutdown, bringing challenges in education to children, parents, and teachers (Futurelearn, 2021). In a study on the implementation of Modular Distance Learning conducted in Cebu, Philippines during School Year 2020-2021, parents had problems related to communicating the lessons to their children (Kintanar and Elladora, 2021.)

The following tables show the summary of the challenges and strategies in the MTB-MLE implementation before the pandemic, and parents' challenges and strategies in teaching MT MOI during remote teaching and learning.

Table 1*Challenges and Strategies in Implementing MTB-MLE Before the COVID-19 Pandemic*

Program Elements	Challenges	Strategies
PROGRAM	Limited background knowledge and misconception of the program Educational system's not so efficient execution of the policy	Inviting the parents to attend meetings for their awareness of the program Informing and educating parents about the program
LANGUAGE	Incompatible practices of language use at home and school Limited use of the MT for academic purposes Low competence of teachers in teaching and using the MT	Parents read their children texts in the MT and use the MT at home to practice the language used at school Reading texts in the MT and listening to local radio programs to improve teachers' competence in using the MT
INSTRUCTION	Lack of training for teachers	Translation of the target language to the more familiar language and use of multilingual teaching and lingua franca
MATERIALS	Lack of relevant teaching Materials Lacking and late delivery of teaching materials	Organizing meetings for parents and community officials to build stronger linkages to encourage donations for materials production Parents provide MT reading materials that the teachers can reproduce

Source: Burton, 2013; Ball, 2010 as cited in Espada and Vivero, 2017; Monje et al., 2019; Williams et al., 2014; Metila et al., 2016 & Lartec et al., 2014

Table 2*Parents' Challenges and Strategies in Implementing MTB-MLE During the COVID-19 Pandemic Remote Teaching and Learning*

Program Elements	Challenges	Strategies
PROGRAM	Lack of background knowledge and misconception of the program	Having consultations and meetings with the school and parents on MT MOI and MTB-MLE program
LANGUAGE	Low competence in the use of MT Low proficiency in the academic register of the MT for teaching	Parents use the MT at home to develop use of MT Using online resources to learn about academic register of the MT, and to explain unfamiliar words in the module
INSTRUCTION	Lack of training in teaching the MT Difficulty explaining lessons in the module due to unfamiliar words Multiple roles at home that affect their instruction to their children	Improving communication with children to make teaching of the MT understandable Using parents' own experiences and culture in teaching, and provision of strategies and techniques to compensate parents' lack of training Providing fun activities and routines for children by singing songs in the MT and playing traditional games that use words in the MT
MATERIALS	Lack of teaching materials at home	Having family members, neighbors, and relatives as content sources of the learning materials Using books used in schools and literary materials available at home

Source: DepEd, 2020; Kolac et al., 2021; Bhamani et al., 2020; Orgiles et al., 2020 as cited in Aykanat & Omeroglu

Theories and concepts related to parents' role in educating their children

Bernard's Spolsky's Theory of Language Management states that language policy has three important components that are interrelated and can explain the language choice of the members of the family; namely: practice, beliefs, and management (Spolsky 2004 as cited in Spolsky, 2009). Using and learning the mother tongue at home where children spend most of their time during the pandemic affects the quality of children's learning. Children use the language that they hear from their parents and become familiar to them. The acquisition of language in children is influenced by their exposure to language practices and beliefs which happen first and are affected by the family (Spolsky, 2009). Parents also affect what their children think are necessary languages to learn or those that they feel superior. Thus, creating beliefs that become acquired at home. In this study, parents are recognized as the primary and significant influencers of children's learning experiences especially in connection to the use of language.

Parents have a special and important role in the education of their children, and language is one of the crucial tools to teach them. They are the ones who shape the child's personality, become the child's role models and benchmarks; and the parents' and children's interaction are necessary for the normal development of the child especially in the early years (T. Marilena, 2015 as cited in Rohita and Krisnawati, 2020). The effect of parents' tutoring to the performance of children in doing tasks alone and self-regulated learning (SRL) had been explored by several studies (Wood et al., 1976; Wood & Middleton, 1975 as cited in PinoPasternak et al., 2010); and based on these studies, parent-child dyads gave children opportunities for SRL engagement by being able to do important tasks and using strategies shown in their

behavior (Gauvain & Rogoff, 1989; Radziszewska & Rogoff, 1988 as cited in Pino-Pasternak et al., 2010).

These theories and concepts explain the role of parents in children's education which are explored by this study. These theories serve as a framework for inferring if the parents have done their roles and conclude what areas need to be improved. First, the social constructivism theory shed light on the importance of studying how parents used strategies and techniques in teaching their children. Second, the interactionist approach talks about children's learning the language from their parents' interaction which is related to this study about how the parents can teach the MT to their children. Lastly, home learning environment and parental involvement emphasize the vital role of parents in the education of their children, which is teaching the MT through effective ways. In this study, the viewing checklist for the strategies and techniques were based on these theories and concepts that discuss interaction, language, and home learning environment.

The next sections explain the theories and concepts discussed above to explain how and why Vygotsky's theory of social constructivism, interactionist approach, home learning environment and parental involvement are related to this study.

Based on Vygotsky's Theory of Social Constructivism, parents have an important role in educating their children. Vygotsky (1962) believed social interaction and cultural influences greatly affect how learning occurs (Miles, 2016). Social constructivism believes that interpersonal interaction and discussion, focusing on the comprehension of students on what is being discussed, leads to effective teaching and learning (Prawat, 1992 as cited in Davis and Smit, 2017). The zone of proximal development (ZPD), which is one of the core constructs of

Vygotsky's theory of social constructivism, emphasizes the role of the instructor in an individual's learning (Davis and Smit, 2017). The sociocultural milieu, the environment of the child, has a significant role in his cognitive development (Vygostky, 1978 as cited in Ansre and Ku, 2017). The learner is exposed to the language of the immediate community where the parent is situated; thus, learning the MT of the family (Ansre and Ku, 2017). The child learns concepts and ideas through the language that the immediate environment uses. The means for accessing knowledge is the language. In this study, the researcher will look at how the MT is used and taught by the parents.

Another theory that this study is related to is the Interactionist Approach posits that children learn language since they want to communicate with the world around them, making language dependent upon social interaction (Khan Academy). The role of parental input in the language development of children was emphasized by social interactionists, parents teach the first words of their children, and they learn by means of imitating them (Gleason and Ratner, 2013). This theory is relevant to this study since the MT, a language that is assumed to be most familiar and most convenient to use by the children, was used by the parents to teach them. In this study, the parents' strategies and techniques in teaching were identified through their interactions in teaching at home.

Home learning environment and parental involvement

Aside from the theory of social constructivism and interactionist approach, concepts on the home learning environment and parental involvement are relevant because the setting of this study was at home and the parents were the participants of this study. An important aspect to teaching at home is the home learning environment which influences the development of the child intellectually and socially

(Crew, 2020). Parents' positive response to child's expressions and vocalizations are important in laying the foundation of children's early language skills (Crew, 2020). Furthermore, having a good learning environment in the child's early years can help him have rich vocabulary, improvement in spelling and high level of literacy (Smees and Sammons as cited in Crew, 2020). Hence, it is important to look at how the parents create the home physical set-up such as use of learning materials, table, chairs etc. to make it conducive for learning and manage it as a learning environment for the children during emergency remote teaching and learning. In this study, the communication skills of parents in using and teaching the MT were explored.

Lastly, the concept of parental involvement influenced the questions that needed to be addressed in this study. Parental involvement is the degree of participation a parent offers in terms of educating their children (Bartolome et al., 2017). There were two main issues that came up due to the level of involvement the parents had in their children's learning in the home -- the first was the sustainable kind of communication the parents used with their children, and the second was the general impact of the parents in creating learning at home (Arriero, 2006 as cited in Bartolome et al. 2017). During emergency remote teaching and learning, the degree of parental involvement in distance learning differed among families (Huber et al., 2020 as cited in Schmidt et al., 2021). According to a study, parental involvement helped in children's academic achievement, but parental homework involvement had been shown to negatively affect parents' emotional well-being (Barger et al., 2019 as cited in Schmidt et al., 2021). Parents experienced much stress with the additional obligation of facilitating learning at home. Although spending more time with their children during pandemic was good for their affective well-being, teaching children at home resulted in diminished emotional health (Lades et al., 2020 as cited in Schmidt

et al., 2021). Children had limited interaction outside their homes while parents could not fully attend to their needs. Parents had to adapt to many changes as they dealt with remote learning of children while coping with the COVID-19 crisis (Cahapay, 2021).

The parents have the obligation of educating their children, even though the child is already studying at the preschool and elementary, from the lowest level of education to higher education (Rohita and Kriswanati, 2020). At the start of the development of children's self-regulatory behaviors, they depended most of the time on their parents in terms of opportunities of doing tasks (Pino-Pasternak et al., 2010). The parents, especially during emergency remote teaching and learning, spent more time teaching their children using the MT at home. Learning about the importance of MT and how to use it can be facilitated by the parents. The abilities of parents in scaffolding properly the academic tasks of their children can affect their academic achievement (PinoPasternak et al., 2010). There were three socioemotional behaviors that parents showed to their children namely: "1) control, 2) responsiveness, and 3) displays of affect that are related to self-regulated learning" (PinoPasternak et al., 2010, p. 221). Children's learning is affected by the way their parents treat them or communicate with them in doing schoolrelated tasks. In a study on parent-child interactions, it was revealed that children had more engagement in self-regulated learning when their parents had good interactions and positive influence on them (PinoPasternak et al., 2010). Therefore, the way the parents interact with their children during the teaching sessions affects learning.

Synthesis

Based on studies, there were many challenges to MTB-MLE implementation in terms of concept, language, instruction, and materials. There were also strategies to overcome them. Unfortunately, another challenge came in December 2019 which was the Coronavirus pandemic that affected every aspect of our life including children's education. Since March 2020, distance or remote teaching and learning has been utilized to continue the education of children. Most parents, if not all, were not prepared to do remote teaching. The parents have become the main facilitators of learning the MT, and the home has become the new classroom in implementing the MTB-MLE program. There have been benefits and challenges in remote teaching learning, but through documentation of parents' experiences, the strategies, and techniques they use, and how they overcome the challenges they experience, we will surely learn from the parents' experiences. We can develop more strategies in teaching and using the MT MOI from Vygotsky's theory of social constructivism, interactionist approach, and home learning environment and parental involvement. Parents' experiences, along with the strategies and techniques they use and benefits and challenges they come across, evolve depending on society's situation. Nevertheless, parents have to adapt to the circumstances for the continuity of their children's education. This experience of parents made us realize the importance of parental involvement in teaching the mother tongue to children, that even as we shift to post-pandemic education the strategies used by parents will still be utilized. The experience taught us that there were alternative ways that the parents could do despite limited access to materials, training, and educational background. One good thing that this remote teaching has brought us is making children closer to their own culture by spending more time using

the language most familiar to them, which is the essence of MTB-MLE. Lastly, documenting these experiences can help parents who choose to homeschool their children.

Conceptual Framework

This study was based on the theory of Lev Vygotsky (1962) which emphasized that learning happens due to social interaction and culture in children's environment (Miles, 2016). Parents, being the main source of information during remote learning, were the main influences of children's academic development. That is why this study aimed to document the experiences of parents and their use of the MT in teaching their children the MT at home during remote teaching, identify the strategies and techniques they used, and what they perceived as benefits and challenges.

By documenting parents' experiences in using the MT during remote teaching in their homes, the research gap in the literature can be addressed especially in records of experiences of Filipino parents during the COVID-19 pandemic. Additional data on the effects of teaching using the first language can enrich language education studies.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Using qualitative research methods to answer the research questions in this study, variables were indicated in the conceptual framework as presented in Figure 1. Each component is described following a top to bottom, left to right orientation.

The framework is composed of five main concepts indicated in the boxes (1) Parents' MT-MOI related experiences during remote teaching, (2) Parents' MT-MOI related strategies during remote teaching, (3) Parents' MT-MOI related techniques during remote teaching, (4) Parents' Perceived Benefits in MT-MOI, and (5) Parents' Perceived Challenges in MT-MOI.

The first box on top shows the parents' MT-MOI related experiences as they taught their children during emergency remote teaching and learning. Data came from interviews and recorded videos of the parents' teaching sessions. This represents the first research question on what parents experienced during the pandemic as they taught their children using the MT.

The second and third boxes on the center indicate the strategies and techniques related to the MT MOI that parents used with their children during remote

teaching. These represent the second research question on the parents' MT-MOI strategies and techniques during remote teaching.

The fourth and fifth boxes on the left and right represent the benefits and challenges that parents perceived as they taught their children using the MT at home. They have discussed their explanation on why they considered them as such during the in-depth interview.

Definition of Terms

The following terms were used in this study.

Mother tongue - This refers to the language that participants in this study frequently used based on the recorded videos of the teaching sessions and interviews with parent participants. For this study, the MT of all the parents were Ormocanon Cebuano and two children's (Nicole and Eric) MT was English and the other two children's (Marie and Fe) MT was Cebuano.

Experiences – These were what parents lived through as they taught their children using the mother tongue at home during remote teaching and learning. Teaching refers to teaching the MT and using it as MT MOI in teaching all the subjects to the child during remote teaching.

Strategies -These were the activities and procedures that the parents did to teach or use the MT to the children. These were identified by viewing the videos of the teaching sessions using the viewing checklist for parents' teaching sessions.

Techniques – This refers to actual teaching implementation, a way of carrying out the teaching activity. This included use of materials, choice of teaching location, the disposition and personality of the parent, etc. These were identified using the indicators in the viewing checklist for parents' teaching sessions and by viewing the videos of the teaching sessions.

Benefits of Teaching the Child the MT and using it as MT MOI – These were what the parents perceived as advantages in using the MT MOI in teaching their children at home during remote teaching and learning.

Challenges of Teaching the Child the MT and using it as MT MOI – These were what the parents perceived as drawbacks in using the MT MOI in teaching their children at home during remote teaching and learning.

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

This Chapter presents the significant components of the study namely: research design, locale and sample, instruments, research procedure, data gathering activities, and analysis.

Research Design

A qualitative approach was utilized in this study to answer the research questions. As qualitative research, the study aimed to know the experiences of parents in teaching their children using the mother tongue at home. Qualitative research is distinguished by its interpretative paradigm that emphasizes subjective experiences and the meanings they have for individuals (Starman, 2013). The study used a case study design. According to Mesec (1998), a case study is a comprehensive description of an individual case and its analysis, including the characterization of the case and its events (Starman, 2013). This study conducted a multiple case study to document the experiences of four parents teaching their children. In multiple case studies, the researcher studied multiple cases to understand the similarities and differences among them (Baxter & Jack, 2008; Stake, 1995 as cited in Gustafsson, 2017).

Case studies allow the exploration and understanding of complex issues by going beyond the quantitative statistical results and understanding the behavioral conditions through the perspective of the participants (Zainal, 2007). The study

conducted parallel case studies since the cases all happened and were studied concurrently (Starman, 2013).

Locale and Sample

The research locale for the case study was Ormoc City, located in the Western part of Leyte that is facing Cebu. Ormoc is second to Tacloban in terms of population in Leyte with 230, 998 people living in the city, with 376 inhabitants per square kilometer or 975 inhabitants per square mile (philatlas.com). It is subdivided into 110 barangays, 31 of which are classified as urban, 10 as urban coastal, 63 as rural, and 6 as rural coastal (designingresilience.ph). This locale meets the study's criterion of having parents with different backgrounds and experiences. Therefore, it was easy to find respondents who met the criteria. The parent participants live in the four different barangays which are located near each other in the city of Ormoc.

Profile of the Participants

The participants of this study were five parents and a grandparent between the ages of 30-58 years old who currently reside within the Ormoc area. There was a grandmother and a husband since one family had the mother, grandmother, and husband as teachers of one child, but most of the time it was the mother who taught the child. The four parents and one grandmother were assigned with pseudonyms to protect their identity: the parent of the Kindergarten child's pseudonym is Meg, and the child is Nicole, and the grandmother is Bernardita; the parent of the Grade 1 pupil's

pseudonym is Jo and the child is Eric; for the Grade 2 parent is Beth and the child is Marie; and for the Grade 3 parent is Amy and the child is Fe. Jo lived within the city while Meg, Beth and Amy lived seven to ten kilometers away from the city proper. They all speak Ormocanon Cebuano as their MT. All the participants also speak Filipino and English. Although their children speak and understand Cebuano, two of the children participants, Nicole and Eric, were trained to speak English due to more exposure to the foreign language and parents' preference. The four parent participants are married mothers and one grandmother is a widow. Jo and Beth have completed their undergraduate studies, Meg is pursuing her graduate studies, and Amy has not finished her college education. Meg is a high school teacher, has two children studying in elementary school, who teaches her children most of the time, but sometimes assisted by the child's father and Bernardita. Jo has only one child, is a home-based online worker who teaches her child full-time at home. Beth is a housewife, mother of three, who is the only one teaching her children. Lastly, Amy is a full-time mother of her only child. Bernardita is an elementary teacher in a public school in Ormoc City.

The following table presents a more detailed summary of the discussion:

Table 3

Summary of Parents' Profile

Parent's Pseudonym	Age	Child's Grade Level and Pseudonym	Educational and Background	Work
Meg	35	Kindergarten Nicole	BS and MA in Nursing graduate, Diploma in Teaching graduate, LPT and pursuing Doctoral degree	Senior High School Teacher
Jo	37	Grade 1 Eric	BS Management graduate	Online Financial Manager
Beth	45	Grade 2 Marie	BS in Civil Engineering graduate	Housewife
Amy	32	Grade 3 Fe	1 year in BS Engineering	Housewife and storekeeper

Instruments

A survey questionnaire, interview guides and observation sheets composed the instruments for the study. All these tools were validated and piloted.

Survey questionnaire for potential participants

A survey questionnaire was used to screen potential participants for the study. The potential participants were recommended by the teachers of three public elementary schools in Ormoc City. The questionnaire consisted of demographics, information about their children studying in kindergarten to Grade 3, language used in teaching at home, and their willingness to participate in the study. The cover letter and the survey questionnaire are presented in Appendix A and B.

Guide for short interview with parents

This tool was for the short interview with parents to confirm and ask for further information they have provided in the survey questionnaire. Most importantly, this tool verified their willingness to participate in the study. The tool asked questions about the parent and child's background information, teaching sessions with the child, and the parent's willingness to participate in the study. Please see Appendix C.

Guide for in-depth interview with parents

A guide for the In-depth interview (See Appendix D) was used during the interview sessions with the parents. The questions covered basic information about the parents such as their educational background and work. The interview had three major parts: questions on experiences of the parents, their skills in the mother tongue and experience in using it in various contexts particularly in teaching or more formal contexts; strategies and techniques they use; and the advantages and disadvantages of teaching their child using the mother tongue at home.

The in-depth interview guide covered at least eight questions that let the parents share about their experiences as they teach their children using the mother tongue at home. The experience at the beginning and as the months progressed was elicited so that parents can describe how the experience evolved. The second part of the interview had six questions about the strategies and techniques they use in teaching. To get information about the strategies, they were asked about the sequence and activities they did during the sessions. For the techniques, they were asked about the materials they used in teaching. The last part of the interview had at least two questions with follow-up questions on what the parents viewed as advantages and disadvantages of teaching their children using the mother tongue at home. Questions were open-ended to let them elaborate on their answers.

Viewing checklist for recorded teaching sessions of parents and guardians

The recorded teaching sessions of the parent participants were viewed by the researcher. A checklist for video viewing made data collection for Research questions one and two systematic. Using The Viewing Checklist for Recorded Teaching Sessions of Parents (See Appendix E), Strategies and techniques that the parents used were identified, and the advantages and disadvantages of teaching their children using the mother tongue at home were deduced from data. For part 1, the checklist included a list of strategies in teaching with examples (Imus, 2018). A column on the right was checked if the strategy was used by the parents, and another column for notes on details about how the parents used the strategy. Next to the strategy table was part 2, the list of common techniques used in teaching: use of realia, use of printed materials, use of digital learning tools, use of handmade objects, use of things from nature, and use of computer applications. Part 3 included the list of statements that can be experienced when teaching children using the mother tongue at home. The parents later confirmed if they perceived them as advantages or disadvantages.

Research Procedure

The following are the research activities presented in three phases. The figure presents the phases which include participant selection, data gathering, and data analysis. Each phase is discussed further below the figure.

Figure 2. Research Procedure

In the first phase of the study last March-April 2022, a letter was sent to the Department of Education Division office requesting permission to ask the teachers in kindergarten to Grade 3 for their recommendation of parents that qualified as participants of the study. The teachers were from one public elementary school in Ormoc City. The four parent participants for this study could already be found in one school. The survey questionnaire was given to these recommended parents and was retrieved two to three days after or within the week that they were given to the parents. From these parents who answered the survey form, the final four parents were chosen as participants of the study based on how they met the criteria stated.

According to Mesec (1998), interesting cases such as contrasting, extreme and exceptional cases should be selected (Starman, 2013). Hence, in selecting the sample, four parents who had contrasting and different cases were selected. The study required the participation of four parents and their children and four teachers of the learners. Four cases were selected to represent the four grade levels, Kindergarten-Grade 3, as the required grade levels that use the Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education. The cases were contrasting and different because they had different demographic backgrounds in terms of their education and work, some were focused on taking care of their children and some had full-time jobs. They also had different views of the use of MT in teaching their children. Additionally, they had different strategies and techniques used in teaching the MT and in using it as MOI. The parents used the MTB-MLE modules in teaching their children and were expected to use the mother tongue in teaching their children. The experiences of the parents were necessary to meet the research objectives. In addition, some information from the teachers was necessary since part of the experiences of the parents was connected to their relationship with the school and teachers. The parents got the materials for teaching, primarily the modules, from the school.

The selection of participants in the case study was based on the objectives of gathering experiences of parents who have children studying in kindergarten to Grade 3 under the MTB-MLE program. Participating parents taught their children at home daily or regularly, they were speaking the MT of their children, and their children were in Kindergarten-Grade 3 in the same public elementary school.

In addition, face-to-face orientation of the selected parent participants was done individually in different venues last April 2022 to discuss what the study was about, the procedures of the data gathering, and how the participants would participate in the

study. During the orientation, documents such as the agreement and consent form (See Appendix E), and the data privacy and confidentiality form were given to the parent participants. The consent and assent forms (See Appendix F and G) were also included granting permission to involve the parents' children in the study. Additionally, the selected participants were asked for their schedule for the in-depth interviews. A step for screening potential participants was also included in this phase in which initial and informal interviews were conducted with each participant about how they taught their children at home.

The second phase in May-August 2022 included face-to-face interviews of the parents during the first week of the teaching session. Transcribing of data from interviews during the interview week was done. During these conversations with parents, video recording of the teaching sessions was discussed so that trials in video recording followed since the parents were requested to operate the video camera on their own.

The third phase, which was implemented in September 2022, was data analysis where identification of themes that emerged from the data collected was done. Once data were available such as records of the interviews, they were immediately transcribed. Themes or categories were identified. The evidence needed to be systematically recorded which has three levels of analysis that include the construction of categories or themes, naming the categories and sub-categories, and developing systems for placing the data into the categories (Merriam, 1998). To make the findings relevant, it had to be decided what from the data were more important and less important (Thomas, 2006).

The data from the viewing checklists were analyzed according to the categories: strategies, techniques and statements in the checklist that were evident in the videos.

Data Gathering Activities

This section presents the main data gathering activities in chronological order.

Interviews

Each participant parent was interviewed through a short interview and in-depth interview with parents. Initially, they were interviewed to confirm their answers and to make sure they qualified in the criteria as participants in this study and to verify their willingness to participate in the study. There was an initial interview of the four selected parents to ask about basic information on their teaching set-up and to discuss how they could record videos of their teaching sessions. This was an informal and conversational type of interview to build rapport with the parents and was conducted face to face depending on their availability and mostly, in their homes. When the participants requested another venue for the interview, the researcher arranged a suitable place for it.

The in-depth interviews of approximately 30-45 minutes were conducted face to face in their homes. An interview guide was used to facilitate the conversation and to get data that answered research question 1 and 3: the parents' experiences and what they considered as advantages and disadvantages of teaching their children using the mother tongue at home. For the interview process, "questions were generally broad and open ended so that the subject had sufficient opportunity to express his or

her viewpoint extensively” (Giorgi, 1997 p. 245 as cited in Bevan, 2014). The language that was used during the interview was Ormocanon Cebuano so that the parents were comfortable to have shared their experiences. Ormocanon Cebuano is the mother tongue and the language used in natural conversations of the parents who were participants in this study.

Recording of home teaching sessions

The aim for this study was to record at least 6 and a maximum of 10 hours of teaching sessions per family for the entire data collection from May-July 2022. During data collection of recorded videos, classes were already about to end, that is why most of the parent participants were able to record only these number of hours. Nevertheless, the collected data was reviewed and was found to be sufficient to answer the research questions. The period for recording the teaching sessions depended on the parents’ respective teaching time and schedule. This study made sure children were protected through identity hidden, faces in pictures were covered, and video and audio recordings were kept confidential. Simultaneously, videos recorded by the parents were retrieved at the end of every recording day or every Friday and were viewed and analyzed by the researcher using the viewing checklist.

The activities of the parents were investigated during the teaching process, and how they performed the duty of assisting their children in the learning process guided by the checklist. The date of recording the teaching session was May to July 2022.

The video cameras that were used were the cameras in cell phones with at least 16 megapixels image resolution, with clear audio, built-in microphones, built-in

memory, and battery that lasted for at least 2 hours. Each family participant was provided with phones, chargers, tripods and cell phone stands.

Provided video cameras were set up in each of the parents' homes, particularly in the place where they hold the teaching sessions. Trial recording with parents was done to make sure that the camera was working, and sessions were properly recorded. The parents were taught how to operate the video camera for recording, and there were trial sessions. For the teaching sessions, the parents and one grandmother were the ones who handled the teaching sessions. During the trial sessions, the researcher demonstrated how to operate the camera for recording. In about 10 minutes, the video recording was stopped, the researcher demonstrated how to stop the recording. The participants viewed the recorded session and checked the quality of the video and if the angles were captured well. Ethics requires proper angling so that the camera does not focus on the faces of participants. The camera also captured what the parent and child were doing. There were at least three trials to make the parents get acquainted with the process of video recording. The cameras were left in their homes during the six-week recording period, but files of the recorded video were retrieved at the end of every week or depending on the agreement of parents and researcher for the frequency per week of data collection. The parents' convenience and preference were considered so that schedules for retrieval of videos were flexible. The parent participant, Beth, suffered a serious illness making her unable to teach her child. However, she managed to continue in July but only had a total of 6 hours of recorded teaching sessions. Upon checking the first videos submitted, they were audible and clear but the texts in the materials that they used

were not so clear. Nevertheless, it was not so necessary as long as their discussion was clear. There was no need to redo video trials with the parents.

After the six weeks of recording the teaching sessions, the viewing checklists were summarized so that these data were shown to each parent participant. Each of them then confirmed if they agreed with the data presented in the checklist.

Data Analysis

To answer the first research question on parents' experiences teaching the MT and using it as MOI during emergency remote teaching and learning set-up with their children, data from interviews were analyzed by generating themes. It was critical to organize the data since a large amount of information was expected with qualitative research (Creswell, 2012). Manual coding was used in analyzing the data from the interviews. Creswell's (2014) steps in analyzing qualitative data were followed. First, data were organized and prepared for analysis which included transcribing interviews, viewing recorded sessions, encoding field notes, and sorting data according to their source (Creswell, 2014). Second, the data were read with reflection and were read critically in relation to how they can answer the research questions. Lastly, coding of data wherein description of the setting or people and categories or themes for analysis was applied (Creswell, 2014).

To answer the second research question, the list of strategies and techniques used by the parents in teaching the MT and using it as MOI were based on the videos that were recorded. The viewing checklist served as a guide to identify commonly done by the parents in the sessions. Additional activities and notable behavior and

statements of the parents were identified and explained further on the spaces provided in the tool. Only the videos recorded after the trial recording were analyzed. Once raw data were transcribed and watched using the viewing checklist, they were read, reviewed, and analyzed. The transcribed interviews were read in detail until the researcher was familiar with their content and could generate themes and events revealed in the text. Using the Checklist in viewing the recorded videos of the teaching sessions, descriptions and narrations of the strategies and techniques were based on the recordings. Since recorded videos were analyzed, multimodality was taken consideration which included body movement and posture, gestures, gaze, print or computer screen layout, design, sound, tactile senses, material resources such as diagrams, photographs, illustrations, 3D models, liquids, video, any material thing that mediates teaching-learning interactions (Lackovic, 2018). By considering elements of multimodality, the mentioned details provided more elaborate information on the verbal and non-verbal cues used by the parents. Looking at the parents' posture, gestures and other nonverbal cues and then confirmed by their statements in the videos, information can be generated about their experience.

To answer the third question on the benefits and challenges of teaching children in teaching the MT and using it as MOI at home, the same viewing checklist was used since part 3 of the checklist had elicited common benefits and challenges of teaching children using MT. In viewing the recorded sessions, data that the parents perceived as advantages in using the MT MOI in teaching their children were considered benefits, while data that they considered drawbacks were interpreted as challenges. For member checking, the data presented in the checklist were then confirmed by the parents if they agreed that these were manifested in the videos. In

addition, this information was taken from in-depth interviews with the parents. Inductive data analysis was used which also utilized generating themes from the responses of the parents in the in-depth interviews. Using the same steps to answer research question 1, the most important categories emerged and were initially noted as themes. Categories were refined by combining or linking them to superordinate categories when the meanings are similar

(Thomas, 2006).

Chapter IV

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND

INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter covers the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data that were gathered to meet the objectives of this study. The sections are divided into categories following the sequence of the research questions: (1) experiences of parents in teaching the MT and using it as MOI in teaching their children during remote teaching, (2) strategies and techniques related to teaching the MT and using it as MOI that parents used during remote teaching, and (3) parents' considered benefits and challenges related to teaching the MT and using it as MOI during remote teaching.

More detailed background information about each pair of parent and child participants is provided at the beginning of the discussion to provide the context to understand the variety of each case. After that, data for each research question are presented first, then followed by the interpretation of results. Data are presented according to cases. To support the interpretation and to supplement the data taken from videos analyzed, related information from the in-depth interviews is also discussed.

Profile of Participants

Parent-child group 1: Meg, Mike and Nicole (Cebuano family which often used English to children)

Meg is a registered nurse and a licensed professional teacher. She is a senior high school teacher and pursues her Doctoral degree in Education major in Educational Management. Meg's MT is Cebuano, but she chose to speak English mostly when talking to her children. Her family had two children of which the older child, Nicole, was the participant in this study. The parents, Meg and Mike, worked full-time, and they taught Nicole when they went home from work and during weekends only. Nicole was a six-year-old Kindergarten pupil who understood Cebuano but spoke English more. Meg's mother, Bernardita, was a public elementary teacher who sometimes assisted in teaching Nicole. Like the parents, she also often used English when teaching her granddaughter.

Parent-child dyad # 2: Jo and Eric (Mother who worked home-based and used English as MT MOI to her child)

Jo is a BS Management graduate who worked full time at home as a virtual finance manager. Her husband is an overseas Filipino worker that is why most of the time it is only her who could teach and take care of her only son, Eric. Jo's MT is Cebuano but just like the first parent-child dyad, she preferred to speak English to her child because she believed he could learn better when English was used. Eric's MT was also Cebuano, but he used English more since he had more exposure to it. Eric was a Grade 1, seven-year-old pupil in a public elementary school which implemented

the MTB-MLE program. He was more exposed to English when at home. As seen in the videos, whenever the lessons were in Cebuano, he showed an uninterested facial reaction. According to Jo, they both struggled in the academic year 2021-2022, that was why she made the decision to transfer him to a private school which did not require the use of the MT in teaching and used English and Filipino only.

Parent-child dyad # 3: Beth and Marie (Mother of three elementary grade pupils)

Beth is a BS Civil Engineering graduate who was a full-time stay at-home mother of three. Most of the time, she was the only one who taught her children, such as during emergency remote teaching and learning. Beth's MT was Cebuano, and she only spoke English and Filipino, when necessary, like for academic purposes. She somehow found the use of the MT beneficial and often used it for teaching. Marie was the second child, an eight-year-old Grade 2 pupil who studied in a public elementary school. Her MT is Cebuano and could also speak and understand Filipino and English. Beth and Marie usually used Cebuano during the teaching sessions even when the subjects were Filipino and English.

Parent-child dyad # 4: Amy and Fe (Full-time housewife and Fe was her only child)

Amy studied BS Engineering for one year and was a full-time housewife and mother to Fe. Fe was the only child, that was why Amy was able to focus on teaching her during remote teaching. Amy and Fe's MT was Cebuano and they only used English when at school or when studying English lessons. Fe's exposure was mostly to the Cebuano language. Amy's exposure to Cebuano was rich since she was able

to read Cebuano newspapers, watch local TV channels that used the MT, and listen to Cebuano songs on radio which Fe enjoyed. Although Amy was a full-time housewife who took care of Fe full-time, she still had a lot of household chores at home. She stated that she had limited time for teaching her at home.

Experiences of parents in teaching their children using the mother tongue and using it as MOI during remote teaching

This section presents the answer to the first research question on the experiences of parents in teaching the MT and using it as MOI during remote teaching. To get the answer for this question, aside from analyzing video data, parent participants were interviewed after the researcher had viewed and analyzed the videos of their teaching sessions. In the following section, individual or distinct experiences of parent participants in teaching the MT are presented first, and then common experiences of parents in using the MT as MOI are presented as themes next.

Meg's effort to address lack of materials in teaching the MT

As a teacher and having a mother who was also a teacher at a public elementary school, Meg found the necessity to use instructional materials using the MT at home. She sometimes used a printer to print additional worksheets and references for Nicole in teaching the MT as a subject. However, this printing of materials did not happen often due to her busy schedule as a teacher during weekdays. According to her *Mogamit ko ug printer sa pagprinta sa mga materyales*

ug usahay mupalit sad mi ug materyales nga nigamit ug Cebuano (I used a printer to print them or sometimes I had to buy Materials that use Cebuano.)

Jo's frequent use of code-switching while teaching the MT

Jo thought that Eric had difficulty understanding lessons in Cebuano that is why during the teaching sessions in teaching the MT as a subject she had to translate almost every word or phrase in English. For example, she had to translate *ihulagway ang mga butang* to describe the things, *pananglitan* to for example, and *ilha ang mga pulong* to identify the words. She also believed that her son, Eric, might be a little behind now because of the subjects being taught in the MT, especially in Mathematics which required the child to learn counting using Cebuano. As seen in the videos, whenever the lessons are in Cebuano, Eric showed an uninterested facial reaction.

Beth's use of practiced method in teaching the MT with older child

Beth's experience was unique since she is a mother of three boys who were all studying, and she was the main tutor for them. She is a housewife and has been teaching his children at home even before the pandemic. According to her, teaching using Cebuano was somehow easy for her since she already knew their lessons since she had been through these lessons. She felt that the lessons were familiar since his older child, who is just one year older than her Grade 2 son, studied in the same school under the MTB-MLE program. What she did was use the same materials and notes for teaching the younger child, Marie, when teaching the MT.

She would just want to teach with ease and flexibility. She did not want to pressure herself and his children to be very excellent. This is how she explained *Gusto nako na ang akong anak makat-on sa natural na paagi parehas anang magstorya lang mi magbinisaya, pero dili kaayu ko mag-effort pagpangita references kung magtudlo ko* (I want my child to learn the natural way like when we are just having conversations in Cebuano, and not exert much effort in finding many references when I teach.)

Amy's experience of teaching the MT the natural way

Amy also has a different profile and thus her experience in teaching her child, Fe, was unique. Since she was a housewife and Fe was an only child, she had more time in teaching and was the most innovative in conducting the sessions. For her case, teaching was not so difficult for her since she has been teaching Fe since preschool. Using the MT in teaching the child was just natural for her to do because ever since she was using Cebuano in teaching Fe. She believed using Cebuano in teaching was a better experience since she did not have to do much translation compared to using English as MT. For her it was not that difficult because *Magbisaya ra bitaw mi sa balay* (We just speak Cebuano at home.) Using the mother tongue in the module was easy when using it as MOI but because of the unfamiliar words it became difficult for them.

The individual experiences show that Meg and Jo had to exert more effort in translating the MT to English since this was their way of letting their children understand the MT lessons. Beth and Amy found the experience not so difficult because the MOI used in teaching the MT was their first language except for the times when it was difficult for them to explain unfamiliar terms. With this, the children also

had different learning experiences because of the different teaching methods of the parents.

Six major themes from the common experiences of the five parent participants in using the MT as MOI emerged from the data: (1) Difficulty and dissatisfaction in using Cebuano MT as MOI, (2) Preference in Using English than the Cebuano MT, (3) Misconception that using Cebuano MT would be easy, (4) Resourcefulness in providing Cebuano Materials, (5) Use of strategies and techniques in Using the MT as MOI (6) Realization that children did not know much Cebuano MT.

Difficulty and dissatisfaction in using Cebuano MT as MOI

This theme indicated that parents had difficulty and were not satisfied in using MT MOI or how they had taught their children using Cebuano at home due to lack of materials in Cebuano, their lack of knowledge in Cebuano academic variety and language pedagogy.

The five parent participants claimed that they had very limited materials for teaching using the MT, they were mostly dependent on the materials from the school or teachers. According to them, they did not buy Cebuano books and dictionary, and they did not have the time to make instructional materials for the teaching sessions. Jo explained: *Wala mi Cebuano nga mga libro sa balay na mabasa sa ako anak. Wala pud mi Cebuano nga dictionary.* (We do not have Cebuano books at home that my child can read. We also do not have a Cebuano dictionary.)

Although the parents and their children were born and raised in a Cebuano-speaking place, they all had a common problem in translating and explaining difficult

words in the modules which used the Cebuano MT as MOI. Some books that were provided for Grades 2 and 3 (Mathematics and Araling Panlipunan books) were also found to be difficult to use because of the Cebuano words that were unfamiliar to parents. This was according to the opinion of one of the respondent parents: *Nakita nako na lisod jud sabton ug i-eksplekar sa akong anak ang uban. Pananglitan, ang word na dignidad o dignity sa iningles.* (I found some words difficult to understand and to explain to my child. For example, the word “dignidad” or dignity in English.). Amy added that she had difficulty in teaching using the MT due to the unfamiliar Cebuano words. She explained: *Tungod sa mga dili pamilyar na mga pulong sama sa Bisaya sa parts of speech kanang pungway na di kaayu nato gamiton, mga termino sa mga kolor pananglit kanang lunhaw, abohon ug uban pa nga mga lawom nga mga pulong.* (Because of the unfamiliar words like terms for parts of speech, mga pungway which we do not always use and terms for colors like lunhaw, abohon and other abstract words.) Jo also added why she had difficulty in explaining the MT lessons in the MTB-MLE subject: *Adunay mga pulong na para nako lisod sabton, samot na sa pag-eksplekar sa akong anak.* (There were words that I found hard to understand, much more in explaining them to my child.)

Teaching their children was not only limited to guiding them in doing homework but teaching all the subjects using the MT as MOI. Only one of the parent participants was a teacher by profession, Meg; the other three parents, Jo, Beth and Amy, had no formal teaching background and experience much more in implementing the MTB-MLE program. The three parents had only experienced teaching their children for assistance in doing assignments before the pandemic. Hence, the teaching sessions were very minimal and did not require the use of DepEd provided modules which used the MT as MOI. For instance, Meg was a licensed professional teacher, she was

teaching senior high school students and was not used to teaching young learners. She believed that there are suitable pedagogies in teaching the MT and using it as MOI for young learners as what she expressed in her comments: *Ang pagtudlo gamit ang Cebuano lahi ra, aduna siguro'y mas insakto na pamaagi sa pagtudlo ani nga wa ko na-train.* (Teaching using Cebuano is also different, there must be appropriate methods on how to do it that I was not trained in.). Another parent, Jo, shared why she was not satisfied with her ability to teach her child using the MT during remote teaching when she said, *"Paminaw nako aduna jud dapat steps ug unsaon pagtudlo gamit ang Bisaya o ang mas angayan nga paggamit sa module."* (I think there should be steps on how to teach using the MT or use the module better.)

Parents wanted their children to learn and excel; and as much as they wanted that to happen despite the pandemic, there were many factors that had to be considered. There were not enough preparations on how the parents could function as teachers who used the MT MOI at home. That was why the parent participants in this study claimed that they were not satisfied with their teaching skills in teaching the MT and using it as MT MOI during remote teaching.

Preference in using English than the Cebuano MT as MOI

Meg, Mike and Jo showed attitudes favoring English over Cebuano MT. This might be closely associated with the politics of language which prefers the use of English rather than the first language. It is a common notion especially to parents that being able to use and speak English can be equated to intelligence. Those who can be easily accepted for school admissions and job interviews are the proficient English speakers. These ideas are influenced by the media, our educational system which might have promoted it, and the Filipino people around these parents who have this

belief. For instance, Meg and Mike had the idea of wanting their child to speak English. They were happy that their child could speak the second language well. Nicole mostly used English at home and school, and she was more exposed to the said language. The child's exposure to languages was dependent on what her parents and teachers provided her with. Accordingly, her parents adjusted to the child's preferred and spoken language. They talked to her in English, even when the lesson was supposed to be using MT as MOI. They translated the Cebuano lessons in the MTB-MLE subject to English and explained the MT lessons in English. In addition, Jo was more inclined to the idea that it is good when the child speaks English well. She also believed that her son, Eric, might be a little behind now because of the subjects being taught in the MT, especially in Mathematics which required the child to learn counting using Cebuano. The participants showed that they had to exert more effort in translating the MT to English since this was their way of letting their children understand the MT lessons.

Misconception that using Cebuano MT as MOI would be easy

This theme revealed that the parents thought that using Cebuano MT would be easy since it is the first language of their children. For Amy, she thought that teaching using the MT was supposed to be not so difficult since it was just natural for her to do because she was using Cebuano in teaching Fe ever since. Having this thought, Beth also was confident to not prepare much when conducting the teaching sessions. According to her, the teaching methods using the MT she used were flexible; and most of the time were thought of impromptu, without much preparation. Teaching with no preparation or plan was difficult for her since she did not know what the lessons would

be. There were times she was asked questions by Marie that she could not answer immediately in the lessons using the MT as MOI. Based on her statement: *Kasagaran, dili ko magplano ug magtuon sa mga leksyon kay Bisaya man amo pirmi gamiton. Wala man magtan-aw namo inig tudlo nako.* (I usually do not plan on how to teach using Cebuano and study the lessons because it is the language that we always use. No one observes us while I am conducting the lessons.) She added that she first thought it was easy to teach using Cebuano as MT because their family is Cebuano. However, as she began teaching using the MT, it was not that easy for her.

Resourcefulness in providing Cebuano materials

It has been discussed that one of the parents' reasons for their difficulty in teaching using the Cebuano MT was due to limited MT materials. The parent participants were resourceful in providing additional materials that use Cebuano instead of just depending on the provided modules. As Jo stated during the interview *Makabasa man siya ug Cebuano nga mga sugilanon gikan sa mga module na gihatag sa eskwelahan.* (He can read Cebuano stories from the modules provided by the school.) Hence, she had to use videos from the Internet when the lessons were the MTB-MLE subject to make Eric feel interested in the lessons. Meg also printed Cebuano materials to supplement the limited Cebuano reading materials.

Use of strategies and techniques in using the MT as MOI

Based on the recorded videos and responses of the parents during the interview, they all used strategies and techniques in teaching Cebuano. Despite their various challenges in implementing MTB-MLE at home, they had delivered the lessons

guided by the instructions in the modules. In the next part of this chapter, the strategies and techniques used by the parents are discussed in detail. For the strategies, the parents used Audiolingual Method, Total Physical Response, Discovery Learning, Task-based Language Teaching, Content and Language Integrated Learning and Direct Method. The prominent techniques they used were Use of Cebuano and English, Non-verbal Techniques and Writing Tools, realia, and study area to teach lessons in the MT.

Realization that children did not know much Cebuano MT

The parents in this study realized that although their children's first language was Cebuano, their children were not knowledgeable and proficient in using it. They directly and impliedly expressed this during the interviews. Meg said that when Nicole was assessed in Cebuano at school, the child said *na-half ako brain* (my brain was turned half). Meg realized that Nicole had a hard time when the text she read in the MTBMLE subject was Cebuano. Jo also mentioned in the interview that when they attended a Cebuano mass Eric told her *wa jud ko kasabot, ma (I really don't understand, Ma)*. This was also what happened during her teaching sessions using the MT with him, he told her about words he did not know about.

Summary and synthesis of parents' experiences in teaching the MT and using it as MOI during remote teaching

The following is a table that summarizes the experiences of the parent participants:

Table 4

Summary of Parents' Experiences in Teaching the MT and Using it as MOI

Themes	Parent Participants			
	Meg	Jo	Beth	Amy
Difficulty and dissatisfaction in using Cebuano MT as MOI	Not trained to teach young learners in teaching the MT and using it as MOI	Difficulty in frequent codeswitching to English when teaching the MT as a subject	Difficulty in translating abstract MT words when using MT as MOI	Not so satisfied due to difficulty in explaining difficult MT words in teaching MT as a subject and using it as MOI
Preference in Using English than the Cebuano MT	Preferred using English when teaching MT as a subject due to belief that using it is better for her child	Influenced by the politics of language, thought that English was more beneficial for her child when teaching MT as a subject	*The theme is not applicable to her Sometimes used Filipino and English when teaching using the MT due to necessity	*The theme is not applicable to her Sometimes used Filipino and English when teaching using the MT due to necessity
Misconception that using Cebuano MT would be easy	Thought that teaching Cebuano as a subject could have been easy if her child was more exposed to it	Thought that using Cebuano as MOI could have been easy if her child was more exposed to it	Believed that using MT as MOI was easy since they were using it	Had the idea that Cebuano as MOI was natural to use and could leave the child alone
Resourcefulness in providing Cebuano Materials	Printed additional Cebuano materials for teaching the MT as a subject	Used the Internet in providing MT materials in teaching the MT as a subject	Used old MT notes of older child in teaching the MT and using it as MOI	Used other MT references in using the MT as MOI
Use of strategies and techniques in teaching Cebuano	Used strategies and techniques to let her child become interested in the MT	Used strategies and techniques to let her child become interested in the MT	Combined strategies and techniques to maximize time in teaching using the MT	Innovative in using strategies and techniques in teaching using the MT
Realization that children did not know much Cebuano MT	Thought that Nicole knows less Cebuano when using the MT as MOI	Thought that Eric had less exposure to Cebuano when using the MT as MOI	Thought that Marie still had to know more abstract Cebuano words	Thought that Fe still had to be more proficient in Cebuano

The experiences of the five parent participants were shown in the videos and were also confirmed during the interview with them. The common experiences in using the MT as MOI indicated as themes taken from the recorded teaching sessions and their repetitive responses were: (1) Difficulty and dissatisfaction in using Cebuano MT as MOI, (2) Preference in Using English than the Cebuano MT, (3) Misconception that using Cebuano MT would be easy, (4) Resourcefulness in providing Cebuano Materials, (5) Use of strategies and techniques in using the MT as MOI and (6) Realization that children did not know much Cebuano MT. The parents' difficulty and dissatisfaction were caused by lack of teaching training, frequent code-switching, challenges in translating and explaining abstract words. They often used English and Filipino when they had to translate and explain Cebuano words. They also had the wrong idea that using Cebuano MT would be easy, but they later realized it was otherwise. Since there were limited Cebuano materials, they were resourceful to use materials they found at home to supplement their activities. They also used strategies and techniques in teaching using the MT so that their children would be interested in the MT lessons. During this experience, they realized that their children did not know much Cebuano MT since they still used more English words and they were not so exposed to the meanings of some Cebuano words.

Discussion on parents' experiences in teaching the MT and using it as MOI

The parents' experiences are still related to the findings of studies on pre-pandemic challenges on MTB-MLE implementation: program implementation, teacher training, language bias, and materials.

In Burton's findings on the challenges of MTB-MLE implementation in the Philippines, teachers and parents were implementing the program in a way that translation was focused since they were not taught well of the program's essence (Burton, 2013). Just like what happened to the parents of this study, they did not have the proper orientation about MTB-MLE's principles, and they were not trained on how to implement it at home.

More challenge is emphasized on the teachers at home, the parents, who did not even have the same backgrounds and training as the licensed professional teachers, plus the setting was at the time of the pandemic when there was the threat of the COVID-19. The success of MTB-MLE is dependent on teacher training as it is one of the factors that can lead to its success (Ball, 2011). A study mentioned in Chapter 2 mentioned that some teachers were not proficient in using the MT that made them not maximize MT usage for academic purposes (Williams et al., 2014). This was similar to the experiences of the parent participants who had to use other languages instead of the MT, aside from the fact that two participants preferred the English language.

In connection to parents' preference, the language bias of parents and teachers before the pandemic is still evident to the participants' experiences in which the politics of language is involved. Some parents believe that English is the more powerful language and a better medium to be used when teaching their children. The parents' experiences varied due to their beliefs and their children's language preferences which

were influenced by them and the people around them. Meg and Jo had to translate the MT to English while Beth and Amy did not have to struggle much on translating to English. It can be inferred that their experiences differ in how they view the MT as a medium of instruction.

With regard to challenges in materials used for teaching the MT and using it as MOI, a study revealed that problems in materials were not having enough teaching materials, unavailability of a dictionary of the MT, and lacking MT textbooks for students (Monje et al., 2019). It can be confirmed that the same challenge on instructional materials in MTB-MLE implementation before the pandemic was still experienced by the parent participants of this study especially that they were at home. They were dependent on the modules provided, and they did not have or had very limited MT materials at home. They all had no Cebuano dictionary, and two of the participants were not provided MT books and other supplementary materials. Some studies had recommended that parents and other stakeholders can help in the provision of materials. In fact, there were parents who took the initiative of buying MT materials that their children could use (Metila et al., 2016). However, for the parent participants in this study, they were mostly dependent on the modules provided.

Parents' used strategies and techniques related to teaching the MT and using it as MOI during remote teaching

Parents as teachers at home during remote teaching were also like teachers in the classrooms who use strategies and techniques in teaching and delivering the lessons. This section discusses the parent participants' strategies and techniques in

teaching the MT, followed by their strategies and techniques in using the MT as MOI. Lastly, the summary table and synthesis of the strategies and techniques follow.

The following were the strategies and techniques of parents in teaching the MT during remote teaching:

Meg and Mike's use of audiolingual method strategies and use of Cebuano and English as techniques in teaching the MT

As Meg was about to begin the Cebuano lesson in the MTB-MLE subject, she opened the module and told Nicole that they would be reading a Cebuano story. Meg had to read the Cebuano lessons in the module. Her way to let Nicole improve on reading Cebuano texts was to let her repeat reading words that she mispronounced. For instance, the Cebuano word *mga* which she pronounced as *mang-ga* which was supposed to be *ma-nga* (those). As part of the Audiolingual Method, the teacher had to use the target language with the right pronunciation so the child could follow him or her. Nicole pronounced the Cebuano words *hibaloi* (know) as *hey-ba-lo-i*, *hangin* as *agin* in a different accent and pronunciation, that was why she had to practice reading more texts in the MT. Meg usually repeated words that the child was unsure in pronouncing like the word *hulagway* (picture).

Meg and Mike had difficulty teaching the MT in teaching their daughter, Nicole. One technique they used was sometimes using the MT when talking and asking her. When she asked in a mix of CebuanoEnglish, the father answered in Cebuano but with more English words. Although he felt that his daughter could better understand when English was used, it was his way of teaching her to understand the MT lessons. Meg and Mike's way of teaching vocabulary to her was by directly explaining the

meaning of MT words. For example, in teaching the MT as a subject she explained what *adlawan* (daytime) and *kagab-ihon* (nighttime) meant. According to them, it was effective when they gave examples and explanations using a mix of Cebuano and English because Nicole listened and would easily remember.

Jo's use of total physical response strategy, English use, and writing tools as techniques to teach the MT

One strategy of Jo was to let Eric use psychomotor skills to learn Cebuano and to not feel very bored. She let him write the Cebuano words when teaching the MT and not only memorize them. She asked him to write *linangkob nga mga pulong* (compound words) in Cebuano such as *kamoteng kahoy* (cassava), *bukog panit* (skinny) and *lunod patay* (die hard). Whenever Eric seemed inattentive already, she let him do some activities that could improve his listening skills using Cebuano language. For instance, Jo found it difficult to teach human body parts in the MT as a subject such as *abaga* (shoulder), *suwang* (chin), *liog* (neck) and *siko* (elbow) using Cebuano terminologies. One strategy she used was to let

Eric watched a video on Youtube, "Human Body Parts in Bisaya" with the body parts stated in Cebuano. Before playing the video, she asked Eric to stand so that both of them were standing. When the speaker in the video stated the body part while pointing to it, Jo let Eric say it again while also pointing at the body part. The steps were repeated until they finished reciting and pointing to all the 27 parts in Cebuano.

For the technique, Jo's way of teaching Eric using the MT was by translation, both translating from Cebuano to English and vice versa. She translated Cebuano words to English and vice versa when teaching the MT. She translated *naglangoy*

(swim) to English. She explained what a calendar meant and translated English words like “months” to “buwan,” “year” to “tuig.” She explained using both Cebuano and English. When Jo asked what he would use to know the dates. Eric answered “calendar” and she corrected him by saying that the Cebuano term for calendar is “kalendaryo.” Additionally, she also had drawn objects to illustrate the meaning of some Cebuano terms like *trayanggulo* (triangle), *kuwadrado* (square) and *mga panganod* (clouds).

Another technique Jo used was the use of English to teach the meaning of the Cebuano words to Eric when teaching MT as a subject and in using it as MOI. She had to make sure he understood the MT words by repeatedly asking about the meanings of Cebuano words. She asked what *porma* (form) was in Cebuano. She gave examples of the word in Cebuano like *rektanggulo* (rectangle), *binituon* (star) and *kasingkasing* (heart). She also asked what *nabalaka* (worried) was. She then asked what *naguol* (anxious) was and gave the English translation. She asked what *baglisi* (underline) was and translated it to English whenever he could not respond immediately.

Beth's use of Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) as a strategy, and use of English and realia as techniques in teaching the MT

The strategy that Beth used during the sessions was the CLIL method which used Cebuano to learn Mathematics. Beth explained what division was and how it was connected to multiplication using Cebuano. Marie learned the process of dividing as she became fluent in explaining the process orally using the MT. For instance, she discussed her solution: *ang walo bahinon ikaduha, mahimong upat* (eight divided by

two is four). As they were solving division, the child learned Cebuano Mathematical terms like *bahinon* (divide), and at the same time learned Math lessons.

As a technique, Beth used Cebuano in explaining why Marie needs to learn multiplication. As they were seated in their living room and began the teaching session, they were talking naturally to each other about happenings at school, about how she was able to answer math problems when she had face-to-face classes. She does this as an introduction to the multiplication lesson, emphasizing the importance of acquiring Math skills for practical use. Beth also used real-life examples in her English lesson on problem and solution, but she used Cebuano as MOI. She gave *wala nagtubong sa manok* (not feeding their chicken) as an example of a problem. This was Marie's daily activity at home.

Amy's use of content and language integrated learning for her strategy, and use of realia and multiple writing tools techniques

Unconsciously, Amy had used Content and Language Integrated Learning Approach as a strategy in teaching Cebuano to her child. She always used the MT as MOI in teaching different subject areas like *Araling Panlipunan* (Social Studies), Mathematics, Science and Music, Arts and Physical Education. Although some of the modules for these subjects use English and Filipino, Amy still used Cebuano in discussing and teaching them. The study of content such as these subjects complemented the development of Fe's MT since the terms and examples for *Araling Panlipunan* were in Cebuano. Some contents of the lessons had examples of local places which used familiar words for the child like *suruyon ta ang Lake Danao* (let us

tour Lake Danao), *mga tulay sa Ormoc* (bridges in Ormoc), *ug ang karaan na mansion ni Dominador Tan* (and the old Dominador Tan mansion).

It was evident in the videos that Amy conducted the sessions in a well-prepared study area with a whiteboard in front, books, study materials, a table, and chairs. Aside from this, she also tried using other venues so that Fe would not be bored with just one location. They had experienced studying in a public library. She had a collection of reading materials such as books and magazines in the MT at home from relatives and friends. Having these materials in their study area made teaching interesting and effective since they had access to pictures of some Cebuano terms. Amy also thought of activities that needed art and writing materials, and they could reach them easily because most of these items were in the study room.

The following are the strategies and techniques of parents in using the MT as MOI during remote teaching:

Meg and Mike's use of non-verbal techniques in using the MT as MOI

Meg and Mike maintained eye contact with Nicole when teaching the MT. Meg looked closely while the child was answering the module.

Mike also used his fingers in teaching subtraction. For example, when Nicole asked how to subtract 5, he responded using his fingers explaining about subtraction using both Cebuano and English words. In addition, Meg also discussed daytime and nighttime using examples that the child can see like pointing outside to show the sun.

Jo's use of audiolingual method and non-verbal techniques in using the MT as MOI

Jo used the Audiolingual Method in using the MT as MOI to Eric since he was not interested whenever the subject was MTB-MLE, or when the module was in Cebuano. In this method, the focus was for him to learn proper pronunciation of the MT words by practicing how to say them. She did this by using the *sugilanon* (short story in Cebuano) in the module "Ang Pagtanom ug Mais" (Planting Corn). Jo read first one sentence, then she asked Eric to read it again. Whenever he mispronounced a word, she let him repeat that word. For the long and difficult words, Jo had to write it and cut the words according to syllables, then she had to read it by syllable. For example, she cut the word *katilingban* (community) to ka-ti-ling-ban. She let him repeat reading the short story in Cebuano text aloud and corrected him when he mispronounced words. This was Jo's way to teach Eric proper pronunciation of MT words by letting him repeat words that she dictated. She segmented long Cebuano words like the word *Disyembre* (December) and *kagab-ihon* (nighttime) and *kalingawan* (hobby). She let him repeat each syllable then let him say the complete word. She also repeated his mispronounced MT words like *ingnon* (tell) and *paminawon* (listen) and asked him to read MT texts with her. She then translated the MT to English to let him understand better, but the focus was on pronunciation. She only used Cebuano as MOI for Cebuano lessons only.

Jo also used non-verbal techniques when using the MT as MOI like she had made sure to maintain eye contact with Eric. She also used facial expression and hands in explaining Cebuano compound words. She showed a frowning face and

scratched her body when stating what *bungag-singot* (prickly heat) means. She used gestures by

demonstrating actions of throwing something in explaining what *bato lata* (a game which aims to hit cans for points) meant but used both Cebuano and English words.

Beth's use of task-based approach, discovery learning and direct method for strategies in using the MT as MOI

Beth used a task when using the MT as MOI to help Marie learn Cebuano better and at the same time integrated arts in their storytelling session using the MT. She asked what Marie wanted to do, and they did paper crumpling while reading a Cebuano story. First, she told her in Cebuano to prepare the materials for their art activity. As she gave instructions in Cebuano, the child followed what she said like *andama ang mga papel* (prepare the pieces of paper). An example of Beth's instruction *Gamita ang mga kamot sa pagkumot sa mga papel* (Use your hands in crumpling the pieces of paper). As many pieces were already crumpled, she told her to arrange them on the bond paper to form a flower. She also helped her do it. By giving instructions in Cebuano, the child could improve her listening skills, process what she heard, and put them to action. In this way, she was learning Cebuano and at the same time enjoyed the activity. To give her the freedom to continue the art activity, Beth read her a short story in Cebuano. After reading the story, she asked her using the MT how the artwork was done. Marie also discussed the process in Cebuano.

For Beth's use of Discovery Learning in using the MT as MOI, there were videos showing Beth letting Marie solve Math problems so that she could learn the lessons using the MT. She let her repeat the exercises like solving Math problems in Cebuano,

using both Cebuano and English languages. She allowed her to answer the module with the Cebuano instruction and gave her time to answer on her own. After some minutes, she intervened and discussed the process of dividing in Cebuano.

Amy's use of direct method and use of realia in using the MT as MOI

Amy used the Direct method in teaching the MT and in using it as MOI to Fe by fully using Cebuano when teaching. She only used Filipino and English when the lessons and modules were in these languages. She did not have to discuss grammar rules in Cebuano but by letting Fe listen to the discussions in Cebuano, she could already learn how to pronounce Cebuano words and respond in the MT sentences. When Amy asked Fe about the lessons about high tide and low tide, *unsa may buot ipasabot ani?* (What does this mean?), the child responded by saying *kanang mohugas ang tubig basta hunas* (it is when there is less water when it is low tide).

Another technique of Amy was her classroom-like set-up for Fe's study area in teaching the MT and using it as MOI. She had a whiteboard in front, and she let her child use a pen and paper as she discussed lessons in the MT. She sometimes let her write MT lessons on the board. The drawings were found in the modules. Together, they had drawn their house using symbols as she taught using the MT.

Summary and synthesis of strategies and techniques that parents used in teaching the MT and using it as MOI during remote teaching

The following is a table that shows the summary of language methods applied in strategies that parents used in teaching the MT and using it as MOI:

Table 5

Methods Applied in Strategies of Parents in Teaching the MT and Using it as MOI

Participants		Methods Applied in Strategies				
		Total Physical Response	Discovery Learning	Task-Based Approach	Content and Language Integrated Learning	Direct Method
Meg	Teaching the MT	/	/	/	/	/
	Using the MT as MOI	/	/		/	/
Jo	Teaching the MT		/	/	/	/
	Using the MT as MOI	/			/	/
Beth	Teaching the MT			/	/	/
	Using the MT as MOI	/	/	/	/	/
Amy	Teaching the MT	/	/	/	/	/
	Using the MT as MOI	/	/	/	/	/

Note. Methods used in strategies in teaching the MT as a subject and in using it as MOI are shown based on the parents' recorded teaching sessions.

As shown in the table, the parents used five commonly used strategies both in teaching the MT and in using it as MOI. These strategies were recognized and identified by the researcher and were unintentionally used by the parent participants. Since the MOI of the modules provided by DepEd was Cebuano and they had to

answer the worksheets using that language, the parents had to use Cebuano in teaching although translation was always used by Meg and Jo. For example, the MT was used to explain the lessons, to emphasize important points in the lesson, to correct their mistakes and so many other ways as listed in the strategies column. Doing these was helpful for the children to learn the lessons using the modular approach and to learn also using Cebuano academically in speaking and writing. All the strategies were used except that: Jo and Beth did not use Total Physical Response in teaching the MT; Jo did not use Discovery Learning in using the MT as MOI, and Meg and Jo did not use Task-Based Language Teaching in using the MT as MOI.

For the parent participants' techniques in teaching the MT and using it as MOI, the following table shows the summary of what they have used:

Table 6

Partici- pants		Techniques							
		Use of MT as MOI	Use of Cebuano /English	Use of Non- ver- bal Tech- niques	Use of MT in Conver- sational Manner	Use of Realia	Shows affect- tion and empa- thy in using the MT	Use of appro- priate teaching set-up	Use of Digital/ Electronic tools
Meg	Teaching the MT	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	Using the MT as MOI	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
Jo	Teaching the MT	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	Using the MT as MOI	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
Beth	Teaching the MT	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	Using the MT as MOI	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
Amy	Teaching the MT	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/
	Using the MT as MOI	/	/	/	/	/	/	/	/

Note. Techniques in teaching the MT as a subject and in using it as MOI are shown based on the parents' recorded teaching sessions.

There were nine most frequently used techniques that parent participants used in teaching the MT and in using it as MOI during remote teaching. All the parents used the techniques on the upper row, except for Jo, Beth and Amy who did not show or rarely showed affection and empathy when teaching using the MT as MOI. In addition, Meg and Beth were not able to use appropriate teaching set-up when teaching the MT. There were videos showing that Beth used the most complex techniques since she had used multiple techniques at the same time, while Jo used the most varied set of techniques.

Discussion of parents' strategies and techniques in teaching the MT and using it as
MOI

The strategies and techniques used by the parents were usually coincidental and they did not mean to implement them at home since they were not trained to be teachers. These were just identified by the researcher since they matched with the activities that they did during the teaching sessions. The parents only had a general idea of the teaching learning process, but they were not conscious of the methods and steps on how to effectively conduct the strategies and use the techniques. It can also be observed that there were only a few strategies used by the parents. This is due again to their lack of training or background in teaching, especially in teaching using the MT. There were parents who implemented a strategy that was not in the proper order and had it mixed with another activity. The techniques they used were mostly unplanned and they used only those that were readily available at home. Their use of English in translating Cebuano words was the only way they thought that their children could understand the MTB-MLE lessons. This resulted in making this a major challenge and concluding that using the MT was not good for their children. Nevertheless, they tried teaching their children according to how they thought they could learn.

Parents' considered benefits and challenges in teaching the MT and using it as MOI during remote teaching

This section presents the answer to the third research question on the benefits and challenges of parents considered in teaching the MT and using it as MOI during remote teaching. To get the answer to this question, the parent participants were asked about this during the in-depth interview. Additional data based on the analysis of the researcher were also included. Parents' benefits in teaching the MT as a subject are discussed first, followed by their benefits in using it as MOI. Lastly, data on parents' challenges in teaching the MT as a subject are presented, followed by their challenges in using it as MOI.

The following are each parent's considered benefits in teaching the MT during remote teaching:

Meg's satisfaction of Nicoles's improvement in using Cebuano

Meg found it beneficial when her child could sometimes speak Cebuano fully even without her instructing Nicole how to say it. Although she preferred her child to speak in English better, she was also amazed and happy when Nicole could speak in Cebuano like *mangaon na ta sa udto* (let us eat during lunchtime).

Jo's pleasure when Eric improved in Cebuano skills

Jo directly admitted that she believed there were no benefits she saw when she used Cebuano in teaching Eric. Hence, she preferred him to speak or use English in learning the lessons. However, there were times that she could tell that it was also advantageous for her son to be challenged to learn another language. It was ironic since the referred 'another language' was her first language, but Eric was not so exposed to it. He often watched English videos on the internet, and he had a lot of English books at home.

Beth found it natural to use Cebuano in teaching the MT

Although some participants did not prefer using the MT, they can still think of using Cebuano as a tool to make the teaching sessions easy and not requiring much effort to translate words to English or Filipino. Beth highlighted these in the following words: *Bisaya man amo gamit pag-istorya mao nga natural ug comfortable ra mi.* (Cebuano is what we use when talking, that is why we feel natural and comfortable).

Amy's ease in teaching the MT to Fe

Amy considered using the MT a natural approach in teaching her child that she did not have to think of translating Filipino and English to Cebuano which was contrary to the first parents' experiences. She thought that having Fe exposed to the first language or Cebuano more was helpful for them to be at ease with using the MT. According to her, *Ang akong anak makatan-aw ug makapaminaw pud ug Bisaya na mga kanta. Sa tinuod lang, mga Max Surban ug Yoyoy Villame ang iya mga paborito.*

(My child can also watch and listen to Cebuano songs. In fact, Max Surban and Yoyoy Villame are his favorites.)

Aside from the parents' considered benefits, three major themes emerged for the considered benefits of the four parent participants in using the MT as MOI: (1) Use of the MT in Teaching Felt Natural, (2) Improvement in Children's Cebuano Skills when MT is used as MOI and (3) Children's Developed Interest in the Cebuano MT when it is used as MOI.

Use of the MT in teaching felt natural

Despite having negative ideas about their experience in teaching using the MT at home, the parent participants liked the idea that their children could already identify words, colors and numbers using Cebuano terms such as *lunhaw* (green), *abohon* (gray), *pungway* (noun), and *hulagway* (picture). Meg mentioned during the interview *makalipay man sad nakaantigo na siya sa Binisaya sa mga kolor* (I am happy that she already knows the Cebuano terms for colors). It amazed the parents when their children could utter words for greetings using the MT like *maayong buntag* (good morning), *maayong adlaw* (good day), *maayong hapon* (good afternoon) and *wala'y sapayan* (you're welcome).

Although some parent participants did not prefer using the MT, they can still think of using Cebuano as a tool to make the teaching sessions easy for their children and not requiring much effort to translate words to English or Filipino.

Improvement in children's Cebuano Skills when MT is used as MOI

Some of the discussed benefits and challenges were limited to the answers of the parent participants during the in-depth interviews. Nevertheless, there were also benefits and challenges culled from the analyzed videos but were not expressed by the participants because of their skeptical views of MTB-MLE. One observed benefit of using the MT in teaching their children was having their children develop the skill of speaking in complete Cebuano sentences. It can be heard that those children who were fond of speaking English had already learned to ask questions in complete sentences like Nicole asking *asa diay ka lola?* (Where are you going, Grandma?) in the MT and they could also answer in Cebuano *Wala pa ko mahuman* (I am not yet done) even if they were not instructed on what language to use in answering.

The parents considered teaching their children the MT beneficial as they started seeing their children apply their knowledge of Cebuano terms in conversations. For instance, Amy noticed Fe used Cebuano when giving change to their buyers in the sari-sari store such as *singkwenta'y singko imo sukli* (P55 is your change). They can hear them use Cebuano terms in daily conversations with family members. They can be heard using *hulagway* (picture) sometimes and Cebuano terms for colors like *itom* (black) and *dag* (yellow).

In addition, it is also an advantage that the medium of instruction used in the module is Cebuano since they can just let their children answer the module independently sometimes. However, Meg and Jo had to be with their children, who preferred English, to assist in answering the modules.

Children's developed Interest in the Cebuano MT when it is used as MOI

The researcher considered their children sometimes had the interest in listening and reading Cebuano text; and that becomes a benefit in using the MT. Evidence of this was shown in the children's way of reading Cebuano stories. For example, when Nicole read her Cebuano modules, she did not complain reading the long texts and even asked for the words' meanings. Also, Marie listened attentively to Beth when she read her Cebuano stories. By using their first language, familiar settings and culture were included in the context of the reading materials. The children were more engaged and could relate to what they were reading. In the videos of Beth and Amy reading to their children the lesson which talked about places in their locality, their children were focused and were either looking at the text or looking at their mothers sharing the Cebuano story. In the middle of the storytelling or reading of the lesson in Cebuano, Marie and Fe asked questions in Cebuano. This shows their interest in the Cebuano MT. For the other children, who did not show much interest in the Cebuano MT, the researcher believes there should just be improvement in the delivery of the lessons on the MT and in the materials used.

Each parent participant shared the challenges they experienced in teaching the MT and using it as MOI to their children. These were also shown in the recorded teaching sessions which they confirmed during the interview with them.

The parents' claimed challenges in teaching the MT are presented in the following section:

Meg's challenge of always translating MT words to English in teaching the MT

Meg's daughter rarely spoke Cebuano during teaching sessions, that was why she always had to translate MT lessons in the module. Every time she read a phrase or sentence in Cebuano, she translated them to English or asked Nicole what the Cebuano word meant. For example, do you know what *buntag* (morning) means? Nicole would answer "morning."

Jo's belief that teaching the MT made it difficult for her child to learn

The parent participants found it stressful that they could not leave their children alone to read and answer the modules because the MOI was Cebuano. This is what Jo shared during the interview: *Dili nako siya puwde pasagdan na mag-answer sa Cebuano nga modules na siya lang.* (I could not let her answer the Cebuano modules alone.) Jo's belief was somehow consistent to what the researcher observed in the teaching sessions since her child was not exposed much to Cebuano that was why she had to always translate and explain in English. However, with more effort and trust in the MTB-MLE program, Cebuano will actually not make it difficult for her child to learn.

Jo's challenge of explaining difficult MT words in teaching the MT as a subject

Jo had a hard time discussing lessons in the MT when there were unfamiliar terms for both her and Eric. She had to use English when explaining them to him. For instance, she explained the meaning of *bungag-singot* (prickly heat) in English. She was not consistent in explaining every unfamiliar word, like she explained the

meaning of “porma,” then “gansang-gansang” was not explained. She explained the meaning of Cebuano terms “compound words” in English.

Beth’s lack of teaching training in teaching the MT as a subject

Beth had no formal training in teaching, much more in using the MT in teaching. She just thought that it was the same as teaching them with their assignments before the pandemic. She was dependent on what the MT module asked them to answer. Her concerns were related to effective teaching because she feared that she might not have done it well. She expressed, *Di man ko maka-explain sa mga leksyon ug tarong gamit ang Cebuano* (I could not explain the lessons well in Cebuano).

Amy’s insufficient materials in teaching the MT as a subject

It was mentioned that Amy had prepared a study area for Fe. However, she still had the same challenge of not having enough MT materials. There were lessons in the MT that she had to show pictures of different land and water forms, she only had English magazines and books used to show her examples.

The challenges of the respondents were very related to the discussed themes that answered research question 1 on MT-MOI related experiences. Their shared challenges were related to their capability to teach using the MT especially when they encountered unfamiliar Cebuano terms. Parents also found these unfamiliar terms difficult to explain to their children even when they searched for their meanings online. They believed there might be better approaches to teaching using the MT to their

children. Aside from parents' challenges in teaching the MT, there were also common challenges in using the MT as MOI as revealed in the following themes:

Explaining unfamiliar or difficult words in using MT as MOI

All the parents claimed they had a common challenge in explaining unfamiliar and abstract MT words. There were concepts and words in the module such as *dignidad* (dignity), *kasinatian* (experience), *pagpaambit* (sharing) that they found difficult to explain such as abstract words and those that they thought were not appropriate for their children's age like the mentioned word *dignidad* (dignity) and some long Cebuano words. Jo shared this during the interview *lisdan man gud siya ug tag-as nan ga Bisaya, ako pud maglisod explain* (She finds long Cebuano words difficult to understand, and I also cannot explain the meaning well). Other parents' difficulty was with words that they understood but they could not explain in Cebuano or in a way that young learners could understand like the word *lunod-patay* (with much effort). According to them, there were many unfamiliar Cebuano words in the textbooks and modules. There were times that they used Google to find the meaning of the words, but they still found it hard to understand much more to explain to their children.

Parents' prejudice against the Cebuano MT or preference for English

During the initial and in-depth interviews, Meg and Jo directly and indirectly expressed their negative impression and prejudice against the implementation of MTB-MLE or the use of MT in teaching their children. Meg did not directly state that she was not in favor of the program, but she mostly used English when teaching her

child. While Jo directly stated from the beginning of conversations and interviews with her, she explicitly mentioned that she did not like that Cebuano is the medium of instruction for the first-grade levels in primary grades. This had become a challenge for them to implement the program at home effectively since they limited their use of the MT. Also, they did not exert more effort in using more strategies and techniques in using the MT. There were teaching sessions showing they were mostly dependent on the instructions of the modules, reading the lessons and answering them only.

Absence or lack of teaching training or background in using the MT as MOI

The parents admitted that they were unsure how to teach their children at home since they had no teaching training or background in teaching. They just had to follow the instructions in the module so that they could finish answering them and be able to submit on time to the teachers of their children. During the interview, Jo expressed her challenge of teaching Eric at home since it was her first time to use the module and use the MT as MOI. She had no teaching experience and her college degree is related to business. According to her, *Ako ra ang bahala unsaon nako, usahay diretso na mi sa pag-answer sa module* (I decide how I will do it, sometimes we just go directly to answering the module). Although Meg is a teacher, she also revealed that she was not confident of the way she taught Nicole using the MT as MOI because she is a Senior High school teacher. Meg said during the interview: *Basin naa jud paagi unsaon na pagtudlo ang Bisaya sa ila kay mga bata ra ba* (Maybe there is a way to teach Cebuano to them since they are young).

Insufficient materials in using the MT as MOI

As discussed in the experiences of parents, the parents claimed that they did not have enough materials in Cebuano. They were only dependent on the Cebuano modules provided by the school. Some of them were not supplied with MT books for using MT as MOI which were supposed to aid as their references in teaching at home. The four parent participants did not have supplemental materials and references in Cebuano such as Cebuano dictionary, newspaper, and magazines.

Summary and discussion on parents' considered benefits and challenges

The benefits and challenges were limited to their responses during the in-depth interview. Additional benefits were discussed based on the implications of the analyzed videos. The considered benefits of the parent participants in teaching the MT were: (1) Use of the MT in Teaching Felt Natural, (2) Improvement in Children's Cebuano Skills and (3) Children's Developed Interest in the Cebuano MT. There were benefits when they used the MT as MOI such as showing children's progress in proficiency in speaking complete Cebuano sentences, improvement in their skills in the first language, and children showing interest in reading texts in the MT. The four themes for the challenges that the parents considered in teaching the MT: 1) Challenge in explaining unfamiliar and difficult MT words, (2) Parents' prejudice against the Cebuano MT or preference for English, (3) Absence or lack of teaching training or background, and (4) Insufficient materials in Cebuano. The parents' implied considered challenges in using the MT as MOI were: parents' misconception of MTB-MLE, lack of training in teaching using the MT, limited time in teaching using MT MOI and not having enough instructional materials that use the MT. As

mentioned in previous studies on MTB-MLE implementation's challenges, the majority of the parents had inadequate background on the program (Burton, 2013). Not having enough knowledge of the principles behind its implementation had led to misconception; and the challenges that the parents experienced could give them negative impressions on the program. One study mentioned that parents were afraid that their children's proficiency of English and Filipino might be affected because of learning the MT more (Metila et al., 2016). The same was true to the expressed ideas of the parent participants, they feared that their children would not be able to speak better English as they were using the MT more. These findings of mentioned studies confirm that misconception of the program has affected how the parent participants taught their children and responded to the interview questions. A study conducted by the Leyte Normal University faculty emphasized that among the difficulties of teachers in MTB-MLE implementation was their unpreparedness in the problems they encounter in teaching the MT such as having students who had exposures to different languages at home and in school (Espada, et al., 2017). For the parent participants in this study, they were also not prepared and not trained to teach the MT and to use it as MOI especially that the transition of letting parents teach at home was during the pandemic. Additionally, they share the same concern that they had to use the MT and teach it, but their children were exposed to other languages especially to English. In connection to having limited time in teaching the MT and using it as MOI, a study during the pandemic stated that parents' multiple roles was the major problem in remote learning (Winingsih, 2020; Rohita and Krisnawati, 2020) which was also true for the parents in this study. The participants claimed that their roles at home and work caused them to be limited in teaching their children. Lastly, problems with MT instructional materials were also experienced by the parents. Among the top reasons

of the schools why they were not implementing the MTB-MLE program, were related to resources for MT materials (Monje et al., 2019). Since the program's implementation, materials have been a major challenge, much more during remote teaching when the parents were left on their own. The participants expressed this during the interview that they were mostly dependent on the modules provided by the school. It could have been different if the parents had more supplementary MT materials such as textbooks, big books, realia, etc.

These challenges were mostly left unresolved since they just had to deal with them alone and without intervention from their children's teachers for example. They did not have the chance to consult with their co-parents although they had groups in messenger. This was the sad truth of parents' challenges that led them to say in the local language "bahala na.

Synthesis of the experiences, strategies, techniques and what parents considered as benefits and challenges

The respondents of this study have revealed common experiences, strategies, techniques, and what they considered as benefits and challenges when they taught their children the MT used it during remote teaching. The commonality and differences of the four cases were evident in how they performed as teachers in the teaching sessions, also considering their profiles and backgrounds since they had been initially interviewed. In addition, they were interviewed again to confirm the details that were revealed in the analyzed videos. Hence, this was how the data were analyzed, getting their viewpoints on their experiences and what they did during those teaching sessions. These data were all connected. In fact, they kept repeating their

answers when asked about strategies, techniques, considered benefits and challenges. It can also be deduced that the parents' experiences were influenced by how they viewed the use of MT in teaching their children.

The parents had used strategies and techniques that they were not aware of and conscious in implementing them. Strategies like Direct Method, Audiolingual Method, Total Physical Response, Discovery learning, Task-based Language Teaching and Content and Language Integrated Learning were identified and named only by the researcher. These were used and applied by the parents, but proper steps were not effectively implemented. The use of techniques such as use of digital tools, writing tools, local stories, study area and other techniques were not maximized so that their children could benefit much from the use of the MT in learning. There were many factors that affected the experiences of the parents.

Finally, the parents' considered benefits and challenges in teaching the MT and using it as MOI during remote teaching were connected to their experiences and the analyzed strategies and techniques they used. For instance, they had to use English and Filipino to explain difficult words in the MT was about using a technique to address a challenge. Using Total Physical Response to address the child's boredom or prejudice in using the MT was to use a strategy to resolve a challenge. Though parents were not trained to teach or did not have the background in using the MT in teaching at home, had challenges on materials, they have managed to continue the learning experience of their children at home.

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This last chapter presents the summary of the study, conclusions derived from the results and findings, and recommendations to improve teaching the MT to children especially with parents as teachers at home.

Summary

MTB-MLE implementation in the Philippines had faced a lot of challenges in its first years of implementation; and with remote teaching during the pandemic when the parents were mostly the teachers using the MT at home, more challenges had been experienced. This study aimed to document parents' experiences, the strategies, and techniques they used, and what they considered as benefits and challenges in teaching children at home using the MT MOI. This attempted to fill the research gap of teaching experiences of Filipino parents in teaching the MT to their children and using it in teaching other subjects during pandemic remote teaching.

The participants of this study were parent-child pairs comprising four cases: Meg and Nicole, Jo and Eric, Beth and Marie and Amy and Fe. The first two parents and their children have Cebuano as their mother tongue, but their ideas in using it varied since they preferred to use English often. Their children studied in the same school when the study was conducted. The instruments used were survey questionnaires to screen potential participants, guides for short and in-depth

interviews, and a viewing checklist to analyze the 34 hours of recorded teaching sessions.

To answer the first research question, aside from analyzing video data, parent participants were interviewed after the researcher had viewed and analyzed the videos of their teaching sessions. Through thematic analysis, five themes were generated as common experiences of the participants. These themes were: (1) Difficulty and dissatisfaction in using Cebuano MT as MOI, (2) Use of languages other than the Cebuano MT, (3) Misconception that using Cebuano MT would be easy, (4) Resourcefulness in providing Cebuano Materials, (5) Use of strategies and techniques in teaching Cebuano and (6) Realization that children did not know much Cebuano MT. Unique experiences of each parent which were presented per case were also identified such as Meg's effort to address lack of materials in Cebuano, Jo's frequent use of codeswitching while teaching using Cebuano, Beth's use of practiced method in teaching using the MT with older child, and Amy's experience of teaching using the MT the natural way.

For the second research question on the strategies and techniques, the viewing checklist for analyzing the videos was used. Six strategies were identified in relation to the use of MT-MOI in teaching: activities applying Total Physical Response, Discovery Learning, Task-based Language Teaching, Content and Language Integrated Learning, Direct Method and Audio-Lingual Method. Using the same checklist, common and unique techniques were recognized. Nine techniques were commonly used by the parents such as the using MT as MOI; using Filipino or English to explain the MT; utilizing of Non-verbal techniques; being conversational in using the MT; showing affection and empathy in teaching using the MT; using

appropriate physical set-up, writing tools and digital or electronic learning tools. Their techniques varied in the specific gadgets, materials, and online applications used.

The third research question was answered through parents' sharing during the in-depth interview and based on the researcher's evaluation of the teaching sessions. They also had common considered benefits and challenges which were very related to what they shared in their experiences. These were the revealed themes for their challenges: (1) Use of the MT in Teaching Felt Natural, (2) Improvement in Children's Cebuano Skills and (3) Children's Developed Interest in the Cebuano MT. Each parent's considered benefits were also presented in connection to children being able to speak full Cebuano sentences, improvement in MT usage, being natural and easy in using the MT. Finally, the parents' challenges were: explaining unfamiliar or difficult words, parents' prejudice against the Cebuano MT or preference for English, absence or lack of teaching training background, and insufficient materials in Cebuano.

Conclusions

The following conclusions are made based on the interpretation and analysis of data:

1. Parents' views on MTB-MLE influence their way of teaching using MT MOI during remote teaching. The parents' misconceptions on the utilization of the program and the use of the MT for their children's early education affected their teaching methods and approaches. The parent participants had varied methods of teaching due to different beliefs in teaching the MT and using it as MOI. Reports from interview data revealed that parents who believed that the MTB-MLE program

was beneficial were motivated to use the Cebuano MT as MOI and tended to have more strategies and techniques used. They were motivated to use better strategies and give more time for each teaching session because they knew the benefits of using the MT in teaching. Contrastingly, data from recorded teaching sessions revealed that the parent participants who were not in favor of using the MT as MOI used few and simple strategies and techniques, because they lacked the motivation and will to do more, because they did not believe in the effectiveness of an MT MOI in the first place. This study confirms that some parents have language bias (Burton, 2013) and provides evidence that could be related to parents' use of more or fewer teaching strategies. Given these findings, parents who are not in favor of the program should be informed about it and its benefits for their children, so that they will use more strategies and techniques.

2. Parents used varied strategies and techniques in teaching the MT and using it as MOI during remote teaching. This study has revealed that the parent participants commonly used five strategies and frequently used nine techniques both in teaching the MT and in using it as MOI. This study confirms that parents used their own way of teaching their children during remote teaching, and provided learning activities for their children (Cahapay, 2021; Rohita and Kriswanati, 2020). Some of these activities were not instructed in the module such as having reading sessions using MT materials that were available at home, which is a good initiative. This also confirms the resourcefulness of parents during remote teaching by using videos from the Internet and accessing Facebook groups and pages to help them in teaching their children at home (Teacher Jen, 2021 & Arzadon, 2020). Using the internet, parents

were able to use the TPR method to teach the MT to their children. The parent participants also used realia that were available inside and outside their homes. Hence, even though most of these parents were not teachers by profession, they tried to exert more effort to teach their children, and some of them even unwittingly applied language teaching approaches and methods through their strategies and techniques. The scarcity of materials pushed them to be resourceful by using resources other than the modules provided. Some strategies and techniques they used would require them to borrow and buy materials and take much of their time. Nevertheless, they were resilient and diligent in using them because they were concerned with the education of their children.

3. Challenges of teachers in using the MT as MOI at school before the pandemic are similar to challenges of parents in using the MT as MOI at home during pandemic remote teaching, implying that there are no discovered effective solutions yet to challenges. This study revealed that parents' challenges are similar to those of teachers': having misconceptions about or lack of knowledge in the MTB-MLE program (Burton, 2013), difficulty and dissatisfaction in using the (Cebuano) MT as MOI due to unfamiliar (Cebuano) terms or words in the modules (Williams et al., 2012), lack of training or background in teaching the MT (Monje et al., 2019), and insufficient MT materials (Espada & Vivero, 2017). This implies that challenges are not yet addressed and concerned stakeholders should reflect on effective solutions to be done.

Recommendations

As mentioned in the significance of the study, this study offers recommendations to stakeholders so that MTB-MLE implementation can be improved in the context of implementing it at home with parents as teachers.

The Department of Education

1. Strengthen policies and programs for emergency remote teaching in general, which includes standard procedures for conducting parent orientation seminars to help them become better learning facilitators at home, and the quality assurance procedures or review of self-learning modules (SLMs) across all subjects. Review and revisit SLMs for remote teaching of MTB-MLE and provide assistance to parents who facilitate learning at home. The modules to be used for future remote teaching can also be improved, so that some content will be easier to use for the parents. Aside from the modules, MT textbooks, if possible additional materials in facilitating learning at home can be provided. They can create guides for teachers and parents, so that parents can understand the modules better and teach their children the correct strategies and techniques. According to this study, parents had difficulty explaining unfamiliar words in the modules they used. The language or words used in the modules, especially those abstract and difficult words to understand, should be written in a glossary at the end of each lesson.

Provide simple training for parents on facilitating learning in teaching the MT and using it as MOI to help parents who teach their children at home, especially for Kindergarten to Grade 3 learners. The homeschooling program of DepEd can get

ideas from the results showing challenges of parents participants. Findings of this study revealed parents' difficulty and dissatisfaction in using Cebuano MT as MOI and realization that their children did not know much Cebuano MT. Hence, the training can include guides on how to make facilitating learning easy and manageable at home, and how to improve children's knowledge of their MT.

2. Revisit the MTB-MLE program. This study presented some difficulties of parents who teach the MT such as explaining abstract concepts and unfamiliar words. The curriculum used to implement the program, including contents and activities that teachers at school use and parents at home use, can be modified to meet the needs of students who are multilingual or who are not very proficient in the first language used in the module or MT materials. For example, alternative activities which use simple methods and available materials in both schools and homes can be provided. The language in the MT materials should be edited to fit what is most familiar in the locality. Ensure the availability of more materials to use for teaching and references that will serve as their guide in the teaching process. The parent participants' common challenge was not having supplemental materials and references in the MT. DepEd may address this by requesting and allocating more funds for MT materials production. The schools, through DepEd's directives, can devise action plans on how to minimize these difficulties by producing more MT books and instructional materials that not only teachers can use but also parents and learners can borrow and bring home.

Administrators and Teachers

1. Improve communication and consultation strategies with parents. Based on the results of this study, parents do not have or lack background on how to teach their children at home. They just had to deal with the challenges in facilitating learning at home and limited support from their children's teachers due to minimal communication. Technology can be used for better communication among administrators, teachers, and parents by creating a localized page on social media most accessible to parents per grade level, so that the virtual community is manageable. For example, resource materials on how to create easy-to-make instructional materials that they can use in teaching their children can be posted and downloaded there. This can also be the means to directly ask specific questions related to teaching the MT and in using it as MOI.2. Provide consciousness raising activities for parents in relation to the program to address the challenge of parents' preference in using English rather than the mother tongue. Examples of these activities are regular fora, short training courses on how to facilitate teaching their children at home, and meetings with parents on the principles of MTB-MLE and how to better apply them at home. This study revealed that some parents preferred the use of English rather than the MT as MOI, indicating that activities like fora about the MTB-MLE program at school which invite experts, teachers and parents who can share relevant information using the locality's MT can be conducted. Through these, parents can be provided with some background knowledge on the program highlighting the importance of teaching the MT and using it as MOI to let them realize its significance. It should be clarified that learning and using the first language, or the MT does not hinder

children's learning of a second language, but even helps them in learning another language.

Parents

1. Sustain the facilitation of the learning process and implementation of the program even when students are back to full face-to-face learning. Continue to use the strategies and techniques they used during remote teaching to supplement what their children learned at school and to sustain the benefits they gained when they were teaching them. This study showed that the strategies and techniques the participants used resulted in some benefits, especially for their children. The parents should plan and prepare the activities better by applying the strategies by searching or asking teachers for some information about them. The physical and emotional bond they have developed should still be continued.
2. Have more open communication with their children's teachers and coparents about resources (hard or soft copy) that they can borrow for
MT teaching at home since this study revealed that the parents had insufficient materials in the MT.
3. Be more resourceful, creative, and diligent in finding ways to make teaching using the MT MOI at home interesting and effective. According to this study, some children participants sometimes got bored in the MT lessons. Look for tips online or learn from their friends and co-parents who have experiences in teaching using the MT as MOI.
4. Take the initiative to improve their language proficiency on the MT. One of the challenges of the parent participants in this study was absence or lack of teaching

training or background in teaching the MT and using it as MOI and difficulty in understanding some MT words. Parents should expose themselves to their MT by reading texts, listening to songs, watching videos online or TV that use the MT.

Other Institutions and Researchers

1. The Local Government Units (LGUs), through their Education Committee members of the barangays, should assist parents who struggle in teaching using MT MOI at home especially during remote teaching. During the pandemic, some LGUs hired graduates of Education courses but still had no license to teach to assist parents who teach their children at home. This endeavor can still be continued for those parents who still have time to teach their children at home, but they have limited capacity on how to do it just like some parents in this study who had no teaching training in using the MT.
2. Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) should train parents and teachers and provide an orientation seminar on MTB-MLE, teaching pedagogies, and strategies. HEIs are mandated to provide extension services to selected communities depending on their needs and the HEIs' capacities. This study presented results on parents' lack of background about the MTB-MLE program and difficulty in facilitating learning at home. The HEIs can have an idea about the needs of parents regarding teaching their children using MT at home and plan for ways to help them.
3. Researchers should conduct more case studies or qualitative studies on parents' different experiences to have more data on MTB-MLE implementation at home. This study showed relevant data on the challenges in the program's

implementation which happened to be the same as the literature cited. It is also good that researchers can conduct case studies with parents who teach the MT MOI and who have less access to technology. There are still many different cases to explore, and it is noteworthy to get qualitative data so that the details of their experiences are revealed.

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APPENDIX A
Request Letter for Recommendation of Potential Participants

March 15, 2022

Mrs. Leah M. [redacted]
Principal I
Ormoc City [redacted]
Ormoc City

Dear Ma'am:

I am conducting a Case Study on "Experiences of Parents in Teaching Their Children Using the Mother Tongue at Home" for my thesis in my MA in Language and Literacy Education at the UP Open University.

Hence, I am requesting your good office to allow me to initially conduct an informal interview to some of the Kindergarten to Grade 3 teachers in your school about the MTB-MLE materials they are using for the learners during the pandemic. In addition, I would like also to ask permission to ask these teachers for the recommendation of parents who will be potential participants of this study.

Attached are my proof of enrollment, university ID and the letter of approval signed by Dr. Marilyn B. [redacted] is Division Superintendent. I am willing to share the results of the study with the relevant DepEd office once it is done.

Thank you very much and I hope this letter merits a positive response!

Sincerely,

Georgina M. Orbeta
Student No. 2004-53937
UP Open University

Appendix B
Case Study on Remote Teaching and Learning During the
Survey Questionnaire for Potential Participants Pandemic

I am Georgina M. Orbeta, conducting a Case Study on “Experiences of Parents in Teaching Their Children Using the Mother Tongue at Home” for my thesis in my MA in Language and Literacy Education at the UP Open University. I am looking for parents who will be part of this study.

Hence, I would like to ask for your time to fill out this survey questionnaire to help me find potential participants. All information you provide here will be treated with utmost confidentiality. Thank you very much!

Name: _____ Age: _____ Sex: _____

Address: _____

Highest Educational

Attainment: _____

College Degree (If applicable)

College/University (If applicable)

Trainings/Seminars attended related to Education/Teaching (if any)

Work (Full-time/Part-time)

Number of children: ____

How many are studying? _____

Do you have children who are in
KindergartenGrade3? _____

If yes, how many? _____

What school are they studying?

Are they using printed self-learning modules at the comfort of their homes? What other modes of learning is the school using?

Who teaches them at home? _____

What is your schedule of teaching your child who is in K-3?

Around how many hours in a day?

Will you still be teaching your children at home in May-June 2022?

Languages Used at Home:

What are the Languages you use at home?

What language/languages do you mostly use at home?

What languages do you speak?

What are the languages of your children?

What are their mother
tongues?

What language does your child use/understand more when studying the lessons?

Will you be willing to participate in a case study which will last for 6 weeks tentatively in May-June 2022?

Teaching Sessions with your child will be recorded for at least 10 hours in 6 weeks.

Signature Over Printed Name

Date Answered:

Appendix C
Assent Form Case Study on Parents' Experiences Teaching their Children Using the Mother Tongue at Home

My name is Georgina M. Orbeta. I am a student of Master of Arts in Language and Literacy Education at the UP Open University. I am inviting your child to participate in a research study about the experiences of parents in remote teaching and learning.

Your child will be included in the video that you will record for at least 10 hours of teaching sessions which will last for six weeks, in May/June 2022. The recording will depend on your schedule of teaching sessions.

You may ask questions about the study at any time.

If you decide to include your child in the study, I will not tell anyone else how your child responds or acts as part of the study. Even if his or her teacher asks, I will not tell him or her about what your child says or does in the study. In addition, your child will receive a simple token once data gathering is done.

Signing here means that you have read this form or that you are willing to let your child be in this study.

Name of the Child Participant:

Signature and Name of the Parent Participant:

Date: _____

Appendix D Informed Consent

PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR

Georgina M. Orbeta
MALLE Student, University of the Philippines Open University
Purok 8, Brgy. Linao, Ormoc City
09281689679
gmorbeta@up.edu.ph

PURPOSE OF STUDY

You are being asked to take part in a research study. Before you decide to participate in this study, it is important that you understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please read the following information carefully. Please ask the researcher if there is anything that is not clear or if you need more information.

The purpose of this study is to document teaching and learning situations at home.

STUDY PROCEDURE

You will be interviewed for 30-45 minutes. You will be recording the teaching sessions. There will be trials on how to operate the video camera so that you can do it on your own in the next six weeks of teaching sessions. The video camera will be provided by the researcher. Simultaneously, your recorded videos will be retrieved at the end of every recording day. You will record at least 10 hours of teaching sessions for six weeks, in May-June 2022.

BENEFITS

There will be no direct benefit to you for your participation in this study. However, the researcher hopes that the information obtained from this study may make you and the other parents realize that your role and their role in educating children is recognized and given attention, that your opinions and experiences matter. Upon your request, the researcher can offer debriefing once the study is done.

CONFIDENTIALITY

Your responses to the survey and interviews will be anonymous. Every effort will be made by the researcher to preserve your confidentiality including the following:

- Assigning code names/numbers for participants that will be used on all research notes and documents. Video recordings will not bear the identities of the parent and child.
- Keeping notes, interview transcriptions, and any other identifying participant information in a locked file cabinet in the personal possession of the researcher.

- The files will be password protected and only the researcher will have access to them.
- All data will be destroyed and deleted after analysis is done. Participant data will be kept confidential except in cases where the researcher is legally obligated to report specific incidents. These incidents include, but may not be limited to, incidents of abuse and suicide risk.

COMPENSATION

The participant parent will receive a compensation of P1,000.00 and a token of appreciation at the end of the data gathering procedure. The child, who the parent teaches in the video, will also receive a simple token.

CONTACT INFORMATION

If you have questions at any time about this study, or you experience adverse effects as the result of participating in this study, you may contact the researcher whose contact information is provided on the first page.

VOLUNTARY PARTICIPATION

Your participation in this study is voluntary. It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part in this study. If you decide to take part in this study, you will be asked to sign a consent form. After you sign the consent form, you are still free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason. Withdrawing from this study will not affect the relationship you have, if any, with the researcher. If you withdraw from the study before data collection is completed, your data will be returned to you or destroyed.

CONSENT

I have read and understood the provided information and have had the opportunity to ask questions. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving a reason and without cost. I understand that I will be given a copy of this consent form. I voluntarily agree to take part in this study.

Participant's signature _____ Date

Investigator's signature _____ Date

Appendix E

Guide for Short Interview with Parents

The interview will be in Cebuano or the mother tongue and language most convenient for the interviewee.

Introduction: Thank you for offering to participate in this study on remote teaching and learning during the pandemic. This interview will take only 15-20 minutes. This will be based on your answers on the survey for potential participants of the said study. I will be recording this interview and all your responses will be treated with utmost confidentiality. Likewise, all the personal information you provide in this interview will be confidential.

What is your name?

What is the name of your child?

Parent's Background Information

1. Based on the questionnaire you have answered, you stated that you are the one teaching your child at home, is this new to you? Or have you been doing this even before the pandemic?
2. How many children do you teach at home? Are you the only one teaching him/them?

Child's Background Information

3. Can you tell me some information about your child who is in _____ (depending on the parent's answer to the survey)?
When was the last time he has been at school?
4. Do you think he is now used to the set-up of having to learn lessons at home with you as her teacher?

Teaching Sessions with the Child

5. How often do you teach your child at home? Do you have a regular schedule? Are you consistent?
6. How long are your teaching sessions?
7. How is the teaching experience so far?

Willingness to Participate in the Study

8. Would you be willing to be part of a study on remote teaching during the pandemic?

State that their teaching sessions will be recorded using a video camera for six weeks.

Appendix F

Interview Guide for In-depth Interview with Parents and Guardians

The interview will be in Cebuano or the mother tongue and language most convenient for the interviewee.

Introduction: Thank you for offering to participate in this study on remote teaching and learning during the pandemic. This interview will take about 30-45 minutes. I will be recording this interview and all your responses will be treated with utmost confidentiality. Likewise, all the personal information you provide in this interview will be confidential.

During the pre-survey I have already asked some of the questions that I will be asking, but this interview will be more detailed and longer for you to explain further about your experience teaching your child at home.

Teaching Sessions

1. What days of the week and time do you teach your child?
Do you follow a regular schedule?
2. How are these sessions determined?
3. Why is this scheduled this way?
4. Where are sessions held? Why there?
5. Can you please describe the physical setup of your teaching sessions?
Is the place conducive to teaching and learning? What makes you say so?
6. Do you have any preparation in relation to MT use in teaching?
7. How long do your teaching sessions last? What are the factors that determine the duration of your sessions?
8. Do you have breaks then come back to teaching sessions?

Experiences in teaching the child using MT at Home

9. How is the experience so far? Can you please share about the experience?
10. Do you find this experience fulfilling? Why or why not?
11. Refer to the answer in the survey questionnaire on the languages spoken by the participant. Ask about the language she uses when teaching and the child uses during the session.
12. Is your child also exposed to other languages, can you describe how you manage teaching your child the MT? 13. Please share your language experience or background. How long have you been using the MT and to what degree? How is your exposure to MT texts or people who speak the MT?
14. Are you satisfied with your MT skills in teaching? Why or why not?
15. What incident in using the MT in teaching your child stands out the most? Why?
16. What do you like about teaching your child in the MT?

17. What is the most challenging for you in teaching your child in the MT?
18. Can you share instances when it was difficult for you to teach the MT?
19. What happens when you have difficulty in the MT words in teaching or in the materials used for teaching?
20. What are your strategies and techniques? Do you switch to another language? What languages do you switch to? Why? When do you observe yourself doing that?
21. What do you think should you improve in to teach your child well in the MT?
22. What incidents will you never forget in teaching your child in the MT?
23. What do you find easy when you use the MT when teaching your child at home?
24. Can you share instances when it was easy for you to teach the MT?
25. Would you like to continue teaching your child in the MT even if the learning mode shifts to another approach?
26. What practices in teaching your child in the MT would you like to continue even after the home teaching set-up is done?
27. Can you please complete this sentence? I realized that for me to good in teaching my child in the MT, I have to _____.

Benefits and Challenges of Teaching Children Using MT at Home

28. Generally, do you think teaching your children using the mother tongue at home is beneficial or challenging to you? Why?
29. What do you find beneficial? Kindly explain.
30. How about the challenges? Can you please share? Provide summarized data from the videos evaluated, let the parents confirm and elaborate them.

Thank the parent.

Appendix G
Viewing Checklist for Parents' and Guardians' Teaching Sessions

Name of Parent: _____ MT of the Parent: _____

Name of Child: _____ MT of the Child: _____

Grade Level: _____ Lesson: _____

Date: _____ Time began: _____ Time ended: _____

Instructions: As you watch the video, put a check in the second column when you observe the listed strategies and techniques used by the parent or guardian in the first column. Write in the Notes' column the details on how these are used by the parent.

Part 1: Strategies

Strategies	Yes	Notes
The parent/guardian:		
Emphasizing Relevance of the MT		
tells the child about the importance of learning and using the MT.		
encourages the child to use the MT		
Using MT in the Learning Process of the Child		
uses the MT as MOI.		
gives a little introduction using the MT to give the child an idea about the topic.		
models to the child how words in the MT should be read/ spoken and lets the child say them.		
uses the MT to explain the meaning of an unfamiliar second language word used in the module		
teaches words and their meanings in the MT to add to the child's vocabulary.		

translates in Filipino, English, and other languages the hard to		
--	--	--

understand or unfamiliar MT words.		
uses the MT to explain the meaning of words in another language to answer the child's inquiry		
uses the MT to emphasize important points in the lesson.		
gives feedback (praise or correction) about the child's use of the MT.		
regulates the child's language usage to let him or her practice the use of the MT during the session		
clarifies the lessons or ask questions to the child using the MT.		
gives the child enough time to process questions in the MT, and encourages the child to answer using the MT.		
uses completion prompts: for example, gives a statement using the MT and lets the child complete it.		
gives examples of familiar day-to-day and real-life scenarios in teaching the MT.		
responds to the child's questions immediately using the MT		
lets the child reflect using the MT (oral or written) what he or she has learned at the end of session.		

Parent's Skills in Teaching the MT as a Language of Teaching and Learning		
--	--	--

The parent		
-------------------	--	--

demonstrates appropriate level of formality by using formal register in the MT		
--	--	--

appropriate for the child's age.		
----------------------------------	--	--

uses or chooses the words fit to he or she wants to mean in teaching the MT.		
--	--	--

uses correct grammar using the MT		
-----------------------------------	--	--

presents ideas logically using the MT		
---------------------------------------	--	--

reads aloud and pronounces MT words correctly		
---	--	--

when necessary, segments long words in the MT and lets the child say them correctly		
---	--	--

reads sentences in the MT with appropriate intonations and pauses that allows the child to understand the meaning of the text.		
--	--	--

uses the correct spelling of MT words in teaching the child		
---	--	--

uses the MT in a lively, enthusiastic, and energetic manner by varying his/her tone, volume, and pitch (For example, in accordance with the emotions conveyed in texts especially in reading stories)		
makes/uses realia, illustrations, graphic/semantic organizers, and drawings to teach the MT		
demonstrates through actions or gestures the meaning of words in the MT.		

Using MT in the Natural, Easy and Fun Way of Learning for the Child

The parent:

talks to the child using the MT in a conversational manner		
makes the teaching sessions fun and interesting by having games, trivia, jokes, etc. use the MT		
engages the child in familiar routines and activities using the MT		
utilizes a mini-role play with the child using the MT.		
shows the child affection and empathy in the MT while teaching		
uses haptics or touch (holding hands or hugging) to show support and praise to the child while learning the MT		

Promoting Local Culture Using the MT		
The parent:		
gives examples of real life situations and scenarios in the community in teaching the MT		
reads or shares to the child a story, poem, song, or history about the locality in the MT.		
connects MT lessons to family and community life.		
mentions local writers, artists, and singers as examples in MT lessons.		
engages the child in making artwork that uses the MT such as drawing, coloring and others that present local people, places, and activities		
Others		

Part 2: Techniques

Techniques		Notes
Physical Setup		
The parent and the child are comfortably situated in an area without or with minor distractions		
Use of table and chairs or furniture in doing the teaching sessions		

The teaching session happens in a well-lighted room or area of the house.		
Use of Tools for Teaching		
Use of Blackboard/Whiteboard and Writing Materials to aid in teaching MT		
Use of Ready-made materials such as flash cards and others for teaching MT		
Use of Realia		
Use of available objects at home that can describe lessons in the MT		
Use of things from the environment or nature that can assist the child in learning lessons in the MT		
Use of Printed Materials		
Use of locally published books, magazines, and other printed materials available at home that use the MT		

Use of dictionary that translates words in the MT to another language		
Using commercially available or parent-made charts to present the lessons that use the MT		
Use of printed pictures to teach the MT		
Use of big books that utilize the MT		
Promoting Local Culture		

Use of local food and festival or activities done in the local community as examples in learning the MT		
Use of stories that mention places and people about the local community		
Use of poems, sayings, quotations, prayers, and songs that talk about the local community or the region utilizing the MT		
Use of visual arts such as painting, drawing and others that show the local culture and the MT words in the artwork		
Digital/Electronic Learning Tools		
Use of radio and television to learn the MT		
Use of computer applications utilizing the MT or to discuss local culture		
Use of sites on the Internet such as YouTube and others to learn the MT		
Use of gadgets such as a cellphone, tablet, laptop, and others to show pictures of concepts and things in the MT or about the local culture, explaining them using the MT		
Others		

***This is the end of the Viewing Checklist.

